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GPG on the validation of the VEs and DTs (for all of the applications in objectives 1 and 2), including detailed guidance on how to apply validation procedures (i.e. statistical procedures for the assessment of differences between calibrated standards and corresponding data from their virtual counterpart) to the VEs and DTs

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DELIVERABLE D5: Good practice guide on the validation of virtual experiments and digital twins

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1 Introduction

The purpose of this Good Practice Guide (GPG) is on the validation of the VEs (Virtual Experiments) and DTs (Digital Twins) which are topics in the ViDiT project, including detailed guidance on how to apply validation procedures (i.e. statistical procedures for the assessment of differences between calibrated standards and corresponding data from their virtual counterpart) to the VEs and DTs.

The applications are technically very different, showing how multiple approaches for different concepts of VE and DT are put to work in different use cases that serve as examples.

The main topics visited in this GPG are

- Virtual coordinate measuring machine validation
- Tilted-Wave Interferometer VE-Validation
- Validation of the virtual flow meter
- DT use case, part made by welding
- Validation of Robotic 3D scanning system
- Validation of the reference rotary table DT
- Nanoindentation DT – Validation
- Internal Arc Test
- Quantum Voltage Standard
- High voltage cable system

The ViDiT project has also produced other guides and publications, some are available on the [project home page](#).

2 Virtual coordinate measuring machine validation

This chapter describes the validation of the virtual coordinate measurement machine (vCMM). First, a description of the vCMM and its (traceable) characterization is given. Then, the measurements performed to validate the vCMM are described. Hereafter, the data processing steps are described, which includes outlier detection, fitting routines and uncertainty evaluation. Finally, the results and conclusions of the vCMM validation are discussed. This procedure and its results are also described in [1].

2.1 Virtual coordinate measurement machine

A vCMM is a virtual representation of a coordinate measurement machine, which measures coordinates of the surface of an object in order to derive geometrical features. See [2] for an example of a vCMM. The idea behind the vCMM is to model error sources and how they influence the measurement data. This includes both systematic, as well as random error sources. Then, the error sources are characterized by traceable measurements, which provide an estimate of the value of the error and its uncertainty. This allows for potential correction of the systematic errors in the measurement data, as well as an estimate of the uncertainty in the measurement data. Finally, the estimate and uncertainty of the geometrical features of the measured object can be determined. In this section, the error sources that are considered in the vCMM are described, including a brief description of the traceable characterization of the error sources.

2.1.1 Kinematic errors

The kinematic errors are errors due to imperfect geometry and dimensions of machine components as well as their configuration in the machine's structural loop, axis misalignment and errors of the machine's measuring systems [3]. The kinematic error model of a CMM is a mathematical model that describes the relations between the functional volumetric errors of a CMM and its individual (or parametric) error [4]. Assuming a machine's rigid body behaviour, it includes the rotations and translations that can occur in the machine parts. Specifically, for each axis, 3 different rotations and 3 different translations can occur. In the case of a 3D CMM, this means a total of 18 errors. Additionally, the axes can be non-orthogonal with respect to each other leading to 3 additional kinematic error sources, for a total of 21 different kinematic errors can occur during a measurement. To characterize the magnitude of the different kinematic error sources and their uncertainty, a calibrated hole plate was used [5]. The calibration is performed over the entire measurement volume of the CMM, leading to an estimate of the kinematic errors that depends on the measurement location. Note that the CMM controller already corrects for kinematic errors, hence the kinematic errors characterized by the calibrated hole plate capture the residual kinematic errors after correction.

There are two possible ways to use the calibration data of the kinematic errors in the vCMM. In the first method, the estimate of the kinematic errors is seen as a contributing factor to the uncertainty. In other words, the larger the estimate of the kinematic error, the higher the uncertainty contribution of that error. In this case, the uncertainty of the kinematic error follows from a combination of the estimate of the kinematic error and the uncertainty of the calibration data. Alternatively, the estimate of the kinematic errors can be used to remove the effect of these errors

from the measurement data. Under the assumption that the kinematic error is fully systematic and no longer present in the corrected measurement data, the uncertainty of the kinematic errors only comes from the uncertainty of the calibration data in this case. Note that in this report, only the former approach is described.

2.1.2 Probing errors

Probing errors arise from uncertainties in the stylus tip size and form, as well as from electronics and sensors in the active probing system. This can heavily influence the measured coordinates, as these are determined by the point of contact between the stylus tip and the workpiece. Upon contact with the object, the coordinates at the centre of the probe are registered, and the measured coordinates are obtained by applying probe radius compensation: the radius of the probe is added in the probing direction. Therefore, any error in the estimate of the probe radius, as well as imperfections on the probe surface or errors due to the electronics and sensors will directly lead to errors in the measured coordinates. It is therefore essential that the value of the probing errors and their uncertainties are determined. This includes an estimate and uncertainty of the probe radius, which affects the probing errors in all directions, as well as a directional error, for which a direction-dependent estimate and uncertainty are required. The probing errors (both constant and direction dependent) and uncertainties are determined by means of a calibrated sphere, see for example [6] for more information.

2.1.3 Workpiece temperature

The temperature affects the shape and size of the workpiece, as the workpiece expands when the temperature increases and vice versa. Therefore, it is necessary to correct for the workpiece temperature, such that all measurements are reported at the same temperature. According to [7], results are reported at the standard reference temperature of 20 °C. As a result, any error in the temperature estimate of the workpiece has an impact on the reported measurands. To this end, the workpiece temperature is measured with (calibrated) temperature sensors during the CMM measurement. The uncertainty of the temperature measurement, as well as the uncertainty of the expansion coefficient of the workpiece, determine the uncertainty contribution of the workpiece temperature. Finally, it is assumed that the workpiece temperature is homogeneous in both time and space. Hence, no temporal or spatial temperature gradients are modelled.

2.1.4 Workpiece surface roughness

Surface roughness of the workpiece can have an impact on the estimate of the measurands, especially for measurands that depend on the coordinates of a few or even single data points. The R_a or R_{sm} value of the roughness can be estimated via roughness tables from literature, which take the manufacturing process into account. In the vCMM, the roughness is modelled by adding random deviations to the measurement data in the direction of the surface normal. The mean of the random deviations equals 0, while the standard deviation follows from a roughness table. For the smooth surface under consideration, this simple approach was judged as sufficient. Note that for rough surfaces, a more complex model may be necessary.

2.1.5 Random noise

Finally, random noise is also considered in the vCMM, which is for example introduced by random vibrations during the measurement. The noise is random in

nature and will therefore differ for each measurement, in contrast to the previously discussed systematic error sources. The magnitude of the random noise depends on the measurement technique and is therefore different for scanning and single-point measurements. To determine the magnitude of the random noise, the reference data of a calibrated artefact is compared to the CMM measurements. It is assumed that the random noise has a high frequency, as its magnitude and direction is different for each data point. Moreover, given the standard deviation of the repeatability in the reference data is assumed to be known. Then, a low-pass Gaussian filter is applied to the reference data to determine the frequency such that the standard deviation of the reference data minus the filtered reference data equals the standard deviation of the repeatability in the reference data. In this work, a ring gauge is used as calibrated artefact, see 2.2.1 for more information. The repeatability of the reference data of the ring gauge is equal to 9 nm. In Figure 1 for a visualization of the filtering process of the ring gauge is shown.

Figure 1: Reference data and its filtered counterpart (left) and the noise that is equal to the difference between the two (right).

A low-pass Gaussian filter with the frequency obtained in the first step is then applied to the CMM measurement data. The standard deviation of the noise is determined after subtracting the filtered data from the measured data. In this work, this is repeated for both scanning and single-point measurements, to determine the random noise in both cases. See the results for all measurements in Figure 2. Based on these results, the standard deviation of the random noise is determined.

Figure 2: Estimates for the standard deviation of the noise for all CMM measurements, where a distinction is made between single-point and scanning measurements.

2.2 Validation measurements

To validate the vCMM and the uncertainty evaluation, tests have been performed with a calibrated reference artefact. A ring gauge which has an inner ring with a nominal diameter of 171 mm was used to perform the validation. The diameter and roundness of the inner ring were determined with a reference measurement and compared to CMM measurements that were processed with the vCMM. The roundness (RONt – peak-to-valley roundness deviation) and diameter of the inner ring were determined from both the reference and measurement data. Finally, the reference and CMM data was filtered by a low-pass Gaussian filter when evaluating the roundness, in order to reduce the effects of noise in the data.

2.2.1 Reference measurements

The reference measurements were performed using a laser interferometer and a roundness tester (Mitutoyo Roundtest RA-H5100), which provided the full profile of the inner ring, with relatively low uncertainty. From this profile, the roundness of the inner ring was determined. Figure 3 shows the results of the roundness measurements.

Figure 3: Profile of the ring gauge, as measured by the roundness meter.

The laser interferometer was used to measure the distance between two points on the inner ring (at 0° and 180°). The reference diameter was defined as the distance between the 0° and 180° points on the inner ring plus the average deviation of the entire profile compared to these points (as measured by the roundness meter).

The reference roundness uncertainty is determined by the uncertainty budget of the roundness meter. The reference diameter depends on both the laser interferometer measurement, as well as the roundness measurement. Therefore, the uncertainty of the reference diameter is the combination of the uncertainties of both measurements. However, the uncertainty of the laser interferometer is significantly larger than the uncertainty of the roundness meter, thus, the uncertainty of the reference diameter is approximately equal to the uncertainty of the laser interferometer measurement.

The measurements have been repeated at three different locations on the ring gauge. One measurement at the top, one in the middle, and the other at the bottom

of the inner ring. This means that the reference measurements have been repeated for the different heights along the cylinder axis, which will be used to compare to the associated CMM measurements.

2.2.2 CMM measurements

The reference measurements of the ring gauge were compared to CMM measurements of the same object, in order to validate the vCMM. The vCMM was applied to the measurement data to obtain an estimate of the diameter, the roundness and their uncertainties. Sections 2.4 and 2.5, describe the procedures of estimating the measurands and evaluating their uncertainty, respectively. To determine the consistency between the vCMM output and the reference measurements, the well-known normalized error was used, given by

$$E_n = \frac{x_{\text{ref}} - x_{\text{CMM}}}{k \sqrt{(u_{\text{ref}}^2 + u_{\text{CMM}}^2)}} \quad (1)$$

Here, the estimates of the measurands from the reference and CMM measurements are denoted by x_{ref} and x_{CMM} , respectively, and their standard uncertainties are denoted by u_{ref} and u_{CMM} . Moreover, k is the coverage factor and was set equal to 2.

The purpose of the validation study is to test the performance of the vCMM, thereby including positions in the CMM volume that may lead to a larger measurement uncertainty. To do this, the measurements have been repeated several times, under different circumstances. First of all, the measurements were repeated at different locations in the measurement volume of the CMM. Most of the measurements are performed in the middle of the CMM, but in some cases it may be necessary to use other parts of the measurement volume (i.e. when measuring a large object). Therefore, the vCMM is validated at different measurement locations by repeating the measurements at 7 different locations, in the middle of the measurement volume, but also in the corners and at elevated levels. See Figure 4 for a schematic overview of the CMM and the different measurement locations.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of the CMM and the different measurement positions.

In addition, the ring gauge was measured in different orientations. By rotating the ring gauge around the vertical axis, effects due to the ring gauge shape can be distinguished from errors due to the CMM. The idea is that effects due to the ring gauge shape rotate between the different measurements, while the effects due to CMM errors remain constant. To this end, the ring gauge was measured 4 times at the center bottom of the CMM (blue ring in Figure 4), where it was rotated by 90° after each measurement.

In total this leads to 11 measurements. However, each measurement was performed both by scanning and single-point measurements. Moreover, three different locations of the inner ring were measured (top, middle, and bottom of the ring gauge). This means that in total 66 measurements were performed, which were compared to the reference measurements.

2.3 Outlier detection

In the measurement data there are sometimes undesired outliers, for example due to the presence of dust on the object. It is therefore necessary to remove these outliers when analyzing the data. This section describes the method to detect and remove outliers.

To detect outliers, first a least-squares circle fit is performed and the residuals with respect to the fitted circle are determined. Hereafter, these residuals are filtered with a low-pass Gaussian filter. Then, the standard deviation of the remaining noise (filtered residuals minus unfiltered residuals) is determined. The outliers are defined as data points for which the difference between the filtered residual and unfiltered data is larger than the standard deviation of the noise multiplied by an

acceptance factor (in this study a factor equal to 5 was used). This process was applied iteratively, until no outliers were found anymore. This means that, after removing the outliers, the circle fit was performed again, and the residuals were tested for outliers. If no new outliers are found, the process is stopped. In Figure 5 an example of this process is shown.

Figure 5: Example of the outlier detection results for one of the measurements.

2.4 Fit routines

To determine the diameter and roundness of the ring gauge, fit routines were applied to the measurement data. Different optimization problems were implemented, including least-squares (LSQ) optimization and maximum inscribed circle (MIC) optimization. In accordance with standard practices [8], the diameter of the inner ring is determined by the LSQ optimization. In LSQ, the sum of squared residuals is minimized

$$f_{\text{LSQ}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \operatorname{argmin}_{d, x_0, y_0} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(r(x_i, y_i, x_0, y_0) - \frac{d}{2} \right)^2, \quad (2)$$

with

$$r(x_i, y_i, x_0, y_0) = \left\| \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \end{bmatrix} \right\|, \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are the vectors of measured coordinates on the x - and y -axes, with x_i and y_i as the coordinates for data point i , d is the circle diameter, x_0 and y_0 are the coordinates of the circle center, and N is the number of measured data points. This optimization problem is solved with the Trust Region Reflective algorithm [9].

The roundness was determined with MIC optimization, in line with the roundness meter. This method aims to find the largest circle that fits in the profile

$$f_{\text{MIC}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \underset{x_0, y_0}{\operatorname{argmax}} \left(\min_i (r(x_i, y_i, x_0, y_0)) \right). \quad (4)$$

This optimization problem is solved by applying Lagrange multipliers. The roundness is now given by the peak-to-valley, which can be derived from the data. The peak-to-valley is defined as the maximum deviation from the reference circle minus the minimum deviation from the reference circle. In this case, the reference circle is given by the MIC optimization. In other words, given the optimized coordinates of the center of the circle x_0^* and y_0^* , the peak-to-valley is defined as

$$P(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}, x_0^*, y_0^*) = \max_i (r(x_i, y_i, x_0^*, y_0^*)) - \min_i (r(x_i, y_i, x_0^*, y_0^*)). \quad (5)$$

Finally, when determining the roundness, a data filter is applied to reduce the impact of noise. To apply the filter, the coordinate data first needs to be converted to distances from the circle center. Therefore, first a LSQ optimization is applied to find the circle center x_0' and y_0' . Then, the distances from the circle center are given by $r(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0')$ for $1 \leq i \leq N$. Hereafter, a low-pass Gaussian filter is applied to the distances from the circle center, where the cut-off frequency is determined in line with ISO ISO-12181-2 [8]. In this case, 600 data points are available, which corresponds to a cut-off frequency of 80 UPR. Finally, the filtered distances from the center are converted back to coordinates

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_i^{\text{fil}} \\ y_i^{\text{fil}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0' + r^{\text{fil}}(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0') \frac{\operatorname{sign}(x_i - x_0')}{\sqrt{1 + d(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0')^2}} \\ y_0' + r^{\text{fil}}(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0') \frac{\operatorname{sign}(x_i - x_0') \cdot d(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0')}{\sqrt{1 + d(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0')^2}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where $r^{\text{fil}}(\cdot)$ are the filtered distances from the circle center and $1 \leq i \leq N$, resulting from applying the low-pass Gaussian filter to the unfiltered distances from the circle and

$$d(x_i, y_i, x_0', y_0') = \frac{y_i - y_0'}{x_i - x_0'}. \quad (7)$$

The filtered coordinates are used as input for the optimization routine defined in (4) and the peak-to-valley definition from (5).

It is good to note that there are two additional optimization schemes available, namely minimum zone optimization and minimum circumscribed circle optimization. These are not described here, as they are not used in the validation study.

2.4.1 Validation of fit routines

To double check the vCMM implementation of the fit routines and in particular to warrant that it computes the same result as the CMM software used in the production environment, comparisons with external software (Calypso) have been performed. For 1000 different samples, the diameter has been determined by an

LSQ optimization, and the roundness has been determined by an MIC optimization, both with the vCMM and the external software. The results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Comparison between output vCMM and external software for diameter estimate (left) and roundness estimate (right).

The differences between the vCMM output and external software for the least-squares diameter estimates are limited and negligible with respect to the uncertainties in the measurement data.

The differences for the roundness are in most cases smaller than 1 nm, except for two samples. In these cases, the external software seems to provide slightly more accurate results, as it provides slightly larger diameters for the maximum inscribed circles (about 0.000045 nm). Given this minimal difference in diameter, it is likely that the vCMM found a local optimum or differences have occurred due to rounding. However, the impact is larger in terms of the estimated roundness, which is equal to around 80 nm in the worst case scenario. In terms of the uncertainty evaluation, the impact is minimal and should not lead to significant differences, as the effect only occurs in 0.2% and the claimed uncertainty is a few factors larger than the worst case error. In case this effect occurs in the estimation of the roundness value itself, it could have more impact given that the reference roundness is around 300 nm. Therefore, it is good to test if large deviations occur between the results of the different measurements. If so, the measurement results should be re-evaluated with the external software.

Finally, it should be noted that the filtering procedure was not applied to the MIC estimate, as described above. Instead, the unfiltered data was used as input for both the vCMM and the external software. The reason for this is that the filtering could not be applied in the external software, due to technical issues. In other words, only the fitting routines have been compared and not the filtering procedure.

2.5 Uncertainty evaluation

The vCMM can be used to evaluate the uncertainty of the measurands. As it realistically simulates the measurement process, it can be used to propagate the uncertainties of the error sources to obtain the uncertainty of the measurement data and, subsequently, the measurands. This is done by applying propagation of distributions, which is numerically approximated with the Monte Carlo (MC) method.

To generate MC samples of the measurands, random values of the errors sources are drawn from their respective probability distributions (as given by the

characterizations described in 2.1). Hereafter, the randomly drawn samples from the error sources are applied to the measurement data via the vCMM. By repeating this process, realistic simulated samples of the measurement data are obtained. Finally, the fitting routines can be applied to obtain simulated samples of the measurands. This way, a numerical approximation of the probability distributions of the measurands can be obtained. From the probability distributions, the standard uncertainty can be derived, as well as other statistical properties of the measurands, such as coverage intervals or asymmetries in the distribution. Note that the vCMM can use either the actual measurement data or nominal data of the measured object as input for this process. The differences between the two approaches will be investigated as part of the validation study.

2.5.1 Bias correction: mean

In some cases, it is possible that a bias is present in the estimate of the measurands. As shown in [2], it is possible to detect this bias using the vCMM and apply a correction afterwards. If one assumes that the vCMM is a realistic representation of the actual measurement process, then any bias introduced by the vCMM should be similar to the bias introduced by the measurement process. In case of the vCMM, we know the input data (and associated estimated measurands) and can compare this to the output data (and its estimated measurands). If there is no bias present, then the mean of the simulated measurands should be equal to the measurands that are estimated from the input data of the vCMM. If there is a bias present, then these two values will differ. The estimated bias is then equal to the difference between the mean of the simulated samples and the estimated measurands from the vCMM input data. Once the bias is identified, the measurands estimated from the measurement data can be corrected by subtracting the bias.

2.5.2 Bias correction: uncertainty

Another approach to deal with the bias is to increase the uncertainty. This can be preferred in case the estimates of the measurands cannot be changed, for example due to compliance with norms and standards. The idea is to increase the standard uncertainty that results from the vCMM, such any coverage interval covers the true value of the measurand, despite the bias. In this approach, the standard uncertainty is equal to the sum of half the bias and the standard uncertainty resulting from the vCMM.

2.6 Results

In this section, the results of the validation study are discussed. First an overview will be given of the normalized errors of the vCMM output compared to the reference measurements. Hereafter, the various additional tests that have been performed will be discussed. This includes the location dependence, orientation dependence, bias correction, kinematic error correction and the impact of using synthetic data versus measurement data as input for the CMM.

2.6.1 Normalized errors

The normalized errors, calculated according to equation (1), of the diameter and roundness for the different measurements can be found in Figure 7. The normalized errors of the $\phi 66$ diameter estimates are all between the thresholds of -1 and 1. This provides a strong indication that the estimates of the diameter and their uncertainties are in line with the reference data. On average, the normalized errors of the diameters are above 0, indicating that the diameter is slightly

underestimated. This could be due to the fact that the kinematic errors are not corrected for but only taken into account in the uncertainty. Therefore, this particular set of true values for the CMM errors could lead to a small underestimation of the diameter.

For the roundness estimates, 4 out of 66 measurements have a normalized error below the threshold of -1. This is an indication that either the roundness estimate is inaccurate, or that the associated uncertainty is too low. In addition, the normalized errors are all below 0, indicating that the roundness is overestimated in all cases. Therefore, it seems that a bias may be present in the roundness estimates and that a correction for this bias (either via the mean or the uncertainty) is appropriate.

Figure 7: Normalized errors of the diameter(left) and roundness (right) for the different measurements.

2.6.2 Location dependence

To test the influence of the measurement location, the measurements were repeated in different positions of the measurement volume of the CMM. It seems that the measurement location does have an impact on the measured coordinates. See for example Figure 8, where three measurements are shown. The two measurements in the center bottom of the measurement volume have similar residuals (with respect to the fitted circle), while the residuals from one of the corner measurements show a completely different pattern. To provide a more complete overview of the impact of the measurement location, Figure 9 shows the differences between the diameter and roundness estimates of all measurements and the reference values, where the colors of the different measurements match the colors of the different measurement locations presented in Figure 4. It is clear that there are location dependent effects, as the differences between the various measurement locations are larger than the differences at the same measurement location. Indeed, the difference between the estimated and reference diameter is quite different when comparing the measurements in the various corners of the CMM measurement volume. This confirms the approach of the vCMM, which takes the measurement location into account when evaluating the kinematic errors. In addition, there are also some effects independent of the measurement location (for example temperature effects), attributing to the differences between the measurements at the same measurement location.

Figure 8: Comparison of residuals with respect to reference circle for measurements performed in the center of the CMM versus the corner of the CMM.

Figure 9: Absolute difference in the diameter estimate of all measurements with respect to the reference diameter.

2.6.3 Orientation dependence

Another way to test the influence of the CMM errors is by rotating the measured object several times after performing a measurement. This way, effects due to shape imperfections will rotate between the different measurements, while effects due to systematic CMM errors will remain the same. In Figure 10 the residuals with respect to the fitted circle of these measurements are shown. The residuals are very similar, indicating that the systematic CMM errors are more dominant than the form deviations of the ring gauge. The measurement uncertainty of a single datapoints for these measurements is approximately $0.8 \mu\text{m}$. The residuals shown in the figure fall within these limits. Since the reference roundness of the inner ring is approximately 200 nm , it is to be expected that the differences between the measurements after rotating the object are similar. If the experiment would be repeated with an object that has a form deviation larger than the systematic CMM errors (for example Multi-Feature Check or industrial workpieces), then the measurements after rotating the object should be able to detect the profile of the measured object.

Figure 10: Residuals with respect to reference circle for the rotation measurements.

2.6.4 Bias correction

The diameter estimate is not biased on average, as the mean of the simulated MC samples is approximately equal to the diameter estimate based on the measurement data. Note that this is in contrast to the claim in 2.6.1, where we observed that the diameter was slightly underestimated compared to the reference data. The main difference between the two claims is the fact that the comparison between the reference diameter and the diameter estimated by the vCMM only takes a single (unknown) realization of the values of the error sources into account. While the comparison between the mean of the simulated MC samples and the diameter estimate based on the measurement data is a comparison over a wide range of potential values of the error sources. The fact that the diameter estimate is unbiased on average, does not mean that every single realization of the error sources lead to a perfect diameter estimate. It does mean that in some cases the diameter is overestimated, while in others it is underestimated, leading to an unbiased diameter on average. In this particular case, the realization of the values

of the error sources seems to lead to an underestimated diameter. But since the true values of the error sources are unknown, we cannot correct for this. We can only correct for cases where the measurand is systematically overestimated or underestimated. This seems to be the case for the roundness estimates. The mean of the roundness MC samples is almost always higher than the roundness estimated from the measurement data. In other words, due to the CMM errors, the roundness is almost always overestimated. This bias can be dealt with in two different ways, by adjusting the mean or by increasing the uncertainty, as discussed in 2.5. The normalized errors of both approaches are shown Figure 11.

If the bias is subtracted from the roundness estimate, then all but one of the normalized errors are within the thresholds of -1 and 1, which means that the roundness estimates are more consistent with the reference data after correcting for the bias. In theory, applying the bias correction could lead to a negative roundness estimate, which is physically impossible. It is likely that the bias is overestimated in such a case, which can be the result of overestimated uncertainty of the error sources. In that case, it is not recommended to apply a bias correction. Instead, the overestimated uncertainty of the error sources will likely result in a sufficiently wide confidence interval of the roundness, such that it includes the true roundness value.

In case the uncertainty is increased, then all but one normalized errors are between -1 and 0. This indicates that the bias is still present in the roundness estimate (as only the uncertainty is adjusted and the roundness estimate), but that the associated uncertainty is in almost all cases sufficient to claim consistency with the reference data.

Figure 11: Normalized errors after applying the bias correction to the mean (left) and uncertainty (right).

2.6.5 Synthetic vs. measurement data

The results above are all based on the measurement data. In other words, the measurement data is used as input for the vCMM to evaluate the measurement uncertainty. In addition, synthetic data is generated and used as input for the vCMM, to test the impact of using synthetic data versus measurement data.

The synthetic data is ensured to be in line with the measurement data, in the sense that the diameter, coordinates of the circle center and roundness are identical. Given the optimal diameter d^* , optimal circle center coordinates x_0^* and y_0^* , and optimal peak-to-valley P^* (all derived from the measurement data), the synthetic data is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_i^{\text{syn}} \\ y_i^{\text{syn}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_0^* + r^{\text{lobe}}(d^*, P^*, x_i, y_i; N_L, \phi_L) \frac{\text{sign}(x_i - x_0^*)}{\sqrt{1 + d(x_i, y_i, x_0^*, y_0^*)^2}} \\ y_0^* + r^{\text{lobe}}(d^*, P^*, x_i, y_i; N_L, \phi_L) \frac{\text{sign}(x_i - x_0^*) \cdot d(x_i, y_i, x_0^*, y_0^*)}{\sqrt{1 + d(x_i, y_i, x_0^*, y_0^*)^2}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

with

$$r^{\text{lobe}}(d^*, P^*, x_i, y_i; N_L, \phi_L) = \frac{d^*}{2} + \alpha \frac{P^*}{2} \cos\left(N_L \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{y_i - y_0^*}{x_i - x_0^*}\right) + \phi_L\right), \quad (9)$$

where N_L and ϕ_L are the number of lobes and orientation of the lobes, respectively, x_i and y_i are the measured x - and y -coordinates, $d(\cdot)$ is defined as in (7), $\alpha \in \{0, 1\}$ indicating that we are studying a perfect circle, as well as a lobed circle as synthetic data, and $1 \leq i \leq N$. The synthetic data is simulated for all measurements using this approach. Hereafter, the synthetic data is used as input for the vCMM to evaluate the uncertainty of the measurands. Finally, the resulting uncertainties for the diameter and roundness from both the synthetic, as well as the measurement data have been compared. The results for $N_L = 5$ lobes and an orientation of $\phi_L = 0$ are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Comparison of the standard deviation following from the measurement data (x-axis) and the synthetic data of a perfect circle (y-axis) for the diameter estimates (left) and roundness estimates (right).

Figure 13: Comparison of the standard deviation following from the measurement data (x-axis) and the synthetic data of a lobed circle (y-axis) for the diameter estimates (left) and roundness estimates (right).

The uncertainties of the diameter estimates are almost identical for all cases. Indicating that using synthetic data instead of measurement data has no impact on the uncertainty evaluation of the diameter estimate. This is not the case for the roundness, however. It varies per case whether the uncertainty of the roundness is higher based on synthetic data or based on measurement data, but the differences

between the two can be significant. It seems that these differences are caused by the profile of the ring gauge in the data. The peak and valley of the profile in the measurement data are typically located at a single location, which is more sensitive with respect to CMM errors. However, the synthetic data contains several peaks and valleys of the same size or no peaks and valleys at all, making it less sensitive to the CMM errors. As a result, the uncertainty based on the measurement data is typically lower compared to the uncertainty based on the synthetic data. This can also be seen from the square root of the mean variance over all measurements. Using the measurement data as input for the vCMM the square root of the mean variance equals $0.34\ \mu\text{m}$ versus $0.33\ \mu\text{m}$ and $0.30\ \mu\text{m}$ when using the synthetic data of a perfect circle and a lobed circle, respectively, as input for the vCMM. In conclusion, we deem the results from the measurement data more realistic, as it is a more accurate representation of the object. This way, the uncertainty evaluation is as accurate as possible.

2.7 Conclusion

This chapter of the GPG presents a validation study of the vCMM using a calibrated ring gauge. The ring gauge has been measured at several different measurement locations in the CMM volume and some of the measurements have been repeated after rotating the ring gauge. The results show good correspondence between the reference data and the output of the vCMM for the diameter estimate of the inner ring.

For the roundness, a bias seems to be present in the estimate, which can be identified using the vCMM. The estimated bias can be used to correct the roundness estimate, leading to full consistency with the reference data. Alternatively, the estimated bias was used to increase the uncertainty of the roundness. This leads to consistency with the reference data in all but one of the measurements, albeit at the cost of higher uncertainty.

Furthermore, it was shown that the measurement location systematically influences the measurement results, most likely due to the location dependency of the kinematic errors. It was studied if the values of the measured residual kinematic errors could be used to correct the measured data, and to lower the calculated uncertainty of the measurand. This appeared not to be possible in this application. The residual kinematic errors may not be stable over time or the uncertainty of these values was underestimated. Therefore, it was not feasible to apply location dependent corrections to the data, as the estimates after the correction and the accompanied reduced uncertainty were not consistent with the reference data.

The difference between using synthetic versus measurement data as input for the vCMM was also tested. There were differences between the two approaches, especially for the roundness estimates. It was concluded that using the measurement data yields more accurate results and is therefore the preferred option. Finally, the ring gauge was rotated several times to distinguish between impact of form deviations versus systematic CMM errors on the measurement data. The repeated part of the data seemed to be entirely due to systematic CMM errors. The form deviations in the calibrated artefact were too low to detect any significant changes between the different measurements after rotation.

3 Tilted-Wave Interferometer VE-Validation

In this chapter of the GPG, the VE of the TWI is validated by measurement of a calibrated reference surface and assessing the results using two different uncertainty methods developed within the project.

3.1 Virtual Tilted-Wave Interferometer

Tilted-wave interferometry is a measurement technique for highly accurate form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces. The measurement system of the TWI [10] [11] combines interferometric measurements with ray tracing, perturbation methods and mathematical evaluation procedures. The measurement setup generates differently tilted wavefronts behind the collimator that illuminate the surface under test, see Figure 14. Optical path length differences are calculated from the interferograms measured at the image detector. To reconstruct the form of the surface under test, i.e., the measurand, from this measurement data, a specific evaluation procedure is needed that requires a VE. The VE for the TWI is based on the principles of geometrical optics and implements all elements of the real measurement setup in a virtual environment, e.g., lens systems, beamsplitters, image detector, collimator, light-source, etc. See also the illustration of the VE of the TWI in Figure 14. Then, ray tracing and ray aiming is performed to simulate the measurement procedure. Given specific parameter values for the measurand and all other parameters involved, optical path length differences are generated by the VE that correspond to virtual replicas of the optical path length differences generated in a measurement under similar conditions assumed.

Figure 14: Sketch of the basic setup of the TWI as implemented at PTB using the PTB simulation toolbox SimOptDevice [3] together with the coordinate system used by the TWI. The two virtual planes EQ and EP are used to correct the model of the interferometer to the experimental setup and are explained in reference [11] in more detail. Source: [11], CC BY 4.0.

The TWI requires a hybrid operation of the real measurement device and its virtual counterpart - its VE - to obtain the measurand. This procedure is sometimes referred to as an embedded VE [12]. For more details on the actual operation and the creation of a reference measurement system for the form measurement of aspheres and freeform surfaces see reference [11]. After adjusting the model to the real experiment with well-known reference surfaces, a subsequent measurement involves the acquisition of measurements from the current surface under test (SUT) in the laboratory and a numerical optimization of a virtual measurand, such that the VE produces (virtual) measurements that closely resemble the real measurements. In a first step, the virtual measurand is parametrized by Zernike

polynomials and the coefficients are obtained during the optimization. Afterwards, a transformation is performed that i) translates the parametric polynomials to pixel values corresponding to 3D coordinates, ii) estimates higher frequency deviations from residuals to the form and iii) performs a fit of the resulting point-cloud into an initially assumed design. The resulting 3D point-cloud of this procedure represents the desired absolute form of the SUT and is the final measurand that is reported. The VE of the TWI is numerically complex, since millions of rays are aimed and traced through an optical system for every creation of virtual measurements. Solving the involved inverse problems, i.e., estimating two parametric wavefront manipulators for adjusting the model to the real experiment, estimating the form of the SUT for the measurement and performing the transformation to obtain the final measurand, requires multiple calls of the VE.

3.2 Uncertainty evaluation

Within the ViDiT project, several methods for uncertainty evaluation have been developed.

In this GPG, the VE of the TWI is validated by measurement of a calibrated reference surface and assessing the results using two different uncertainty evaluation methods: A Bayesian uncertainty evaluation method and an approach based on the law of propagation of uncertainties (LPU), which can be seen as a JCGM:GUM-compliant uncertainty evaluation method.

3.2.1 Bayesian uncertainty evaluation method

For uncertainty evaluation involving real measurement data and the VE of the TWI, a Bayesian approach was developed in [12] for a simplified version of the TWI. Consider also the detailed description and discussion in the Good Practice Guide D1 [13] for more insight into the approach. The same uncertainty evaluation approach will also be used for validation in this document.

In particular, the Bayesian uncertainty evaluation approach considers the VE of the TWI as a statistical model

$$x | Y, Z, \sigma^2 \sim N(g(Y, Z), \sigma^2 I),$$

where the forward model $g(Y, Z)$ maps deterministically the measurand Y , i.e. the form of the SUT, and the additional input parameters Z , e.g. the position and orientation of lenses in the instrument, to the observed optical path length differences (OPDs) x . In this GPG, it is assumed that the observation follows a normal distribution with some noise on the OPDs with standard deviation σ . The normality assumption allows for analytical computations, however, the non-linear and highly complex map $g(Y, Z)$, which implement ray-tracing and ray-aiming through the complete optical system of the TWI, allows for a realistic modelling of the real measurement instrument. With some computations and assuming a non-informative prior distribution for the measurand $\pi(Y) \propto 1$, i.e. the parametric polynomial coefficients of the SUT, an approximate covariance has been obtained that can be computed numerically by a Monte Carlo approximation of the following integral

$$U = \int \sigma^2 (J^T J)^{-1} + \left(\theta(Z) - \theta(\hat{Z}) \right) \left(\theta(Z) - \theta(\hat{Z}) \right) d\pi(Z).$$

The Jacobian matrix J is the partial derivative of the forward model function $g(Y, Z)$ with respect to the measurand, evaluated at the usual TWI estimate (obtained via non-linear optimization of a least-squares problem) $\theta(\hat{Z})$, where the specific value for the input parameters \hat{Z} has been obtained from a previous model correction procedure. In contrast, the value for the measurand $\theta(Z)$ is specifically obtained by

solving the same optimization problem, but with a slightly distorted optical system, which is represented by the value of Z that has been drawn from the state of knowledge distribution $\pi(Z)$ for the parameter Z obtained from expert knowledge. The resulting standard uncertainty for the measurand can be obtained by taking the square root of the diagonal entries of the covariance matrix U . For more details on this approach, it is referred to [11] and [12].

3.2.2 LPU uncertainty evaluation method

The developments in this section implement a simplified, i.e., linearized variant of the tilted-wave interferometer (TWI) and provide uncertainty evaluation for this simplified model. The purpose of this section is therefore not the accurate representation of the measurement principle of the TWI, but an exemplary consideration of different uncertainty evaluation procedures when dealing with VEs. Important concepts, such as the heads-up model correction, higher-frequency terms and post-processing of the form obtained (i.e. correction of the surface positioning), are not included in this study. Hence, the results are not representative of the actual TWI and may differ significantly from uncertainties obtained in real experiments. Unless otherwise noted, the VE of the TWI in this section refers to this simplified and linearized version.

The simplified VE of the TWI in this section is modeled as:

$$X = g(\theta, Z) + \varepsilon = A_{\theta}\theta + A_Z Z + \varepsilon$$

Here:

- A_{θ} and A_Z are matrices representing different parameter influences (analytically or numerically obtained),
- θ is the measurand vector, in this case it comprises a limited set of polynomial coefficients and the position of the SUT in x-y direction,
- Z is a multivariate parameter vector with additional parameter influences,
- ε is multivariate Gaussian noise with standard deviation σ

Due to the linearity of the model, one particular choice of the measurement model can be derived from the VE by inversion as:

$$\theta = A_{\theta}^{+} (X - A_Z Z)$$

where A_{θ}^{+} is the pseudoinverse of the matrix A_{θ} . It is important to note that this choice of the measurement model is done in accordance to the choice of the VE. Alternative measurement models can be derived from expert knowledge and by other means. It is nevertheless common (but not always correct) to interpret a measurement model as a partial inverse of an observation model.

For this validation of the VE, we employ the approach “LPU using the VE” from the Good Practice Guide D1 [13]. The resulting covariance of this approach can, due to the linearity of the measurement model and the VE, be expressed as follows:

$$U_{\theta} = \sigma^2 A_{\theta}^{+} (A_{\theta}^{+})^T + A_{\theta}^{+} A_Z U_Z A_Z^T (A_{\theta}^{+})^T,$$

Where U_Z denotes the covariance matrix of the input quantities Z .

3.2.3 Application to TWI

During this project, some simplifications were made to the TWI application to develop the uncertainty methods (see Good Practice Guide D1 [13]) and only a limited number of key influencing factors are considered for uncertainty estimation. The main assumptions made are repeated and the considered key influencing factors for uncertainty estimation are named in the following to be able to explain the results of this GPG.

In the forward model, the parameter θ represents the description for the form of the

SUT together with its position within the setup. The form is parametrized by the design description (for an asphere, e.g., the aspherical formula), Zernike polynomials, which are commonly employed to describe variations in optics, and a non-parametric model correction term that can reflect higher-frequency terms of the surface form. Moreover, θ comprises a set of latent variables that are required for an efficient solution of the following inverse problem. Each patch of the acquired interferograms has an offset value corresponding to a shift of the OPDs of that patch, since the OPDs of each patch can only be calculated from the measurement data up to an unknown offset value. The multivariate parameter Z collects additional parameters of the experiment that are required to replicate the TWI measurements in a virtual environment, i.e., the configurations of the lens-systems, the position of the collimator and CCD, the wavelength of the laser employed, the parameters of the model adjustment, to name just a few. For details on the elements of θ and Z cf. e.g [11], [12]. A list of parameters considered in this GPG for uncertainty estimation is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Quantities and their assumed uncertainties used in the application tilted-wave interferometer within the project. In the column 'Quantity', the general symbols for VEs are used, whereas the column 'Pseudonym' introduces more context specific variable names.

Quantity	Pseudonym	Value	Unit	Remark
X		-	[m]	Optical path differences (OPDs) extracted from the TWI measurement data. Capital X denotes the quantity and x the actual observation.
Y	θ	-	[m]	Multivariate measurand: surface form and position parameters
Z_0	Δz	0	[m]	Deviation of SUT position in z -direction
Z_1	$\Delta \alpha$	0	[rad]	Deviation of SUT orientation in α -direction
Z_2	$\Delta \beta$	0	[rad]	Deviation of SUT orientation in β -direction
Z_3	$\Delta \gamma$	0	[rad]	Deviation of SUT orientation in γ -direction
u_x	σ	1×10^{-8}	[m]	Standard uncertainty of OPDs, i.e. assumed noise
u_{y0}		5×10^{-7}	[m]	Standard uncertainty in x -position of the SUT (included in Y)
u_{y1}		5×10^{-7}	[m]	Standard uncertainty in y -position of the SUT (included in Y)
u_{z0}		1×10^{-6}	[m]	Standard uncertainty in Z_0
u_{z1}		3×10^{-5}	[rad]	Standard uncertainty in Z_1
u_{z2}		3×10^{-5}	[rad]	Standard uncertainty in Z_2
u_{z3}		3×10^{-5}	[rad]	Standard uncertainty in Z_3

It is to note that the list of parameters and uncertainty sources in Table 1 is not exhaustive and many more parameters are known to influence the uncertainty of the TWI, e.g., uncertainty introduced due to the model correction procedure (note that in contrast to [12], the covariance matrix of the model correction parameters is not included here), the form of the reference surfaces used for the correction of the model (leading to model errors), ambient conditions, the wavelength of the laser (if not measured with high accuracy) and other parameters, see e.g. [10], [14]. Also, a realistic determination of the standard deviation of the influencing factors is

challenging and subject to future research. Here, only rough orders of magnitude are chosen in order to demonstrate the methods developed in the project.

3.3 Validation Procedure

3.3.1 Validation measurements

Since the measurement result of the TWI includes a VE, the VE can be validated by performing real measurements and comparing the results (or characteristic parts of them) with reference measurements. Therefore, in the following, a calibrated spherical section is used for the validation of TWI measurements. The traceable reference measurements of the spherical section consists of two different measurements at two different setups at PTB: One measurement setup is used to measure the absolute radius of the spherical surface, and the other measurement setup is used to measure the sphericity, i.e. the deviation from an ideal spherical surface.

Figure 15: The form of a spherical section can be divided into the form given by the absolute radius and the form given by the sphericity, i.e. the deviation from an ideal (best-fit) sphere.

The radius of a spherical section can be measured at PTB's radius measurement bench. The measurement principle uses an interferometer setup to align the surface into two distinct positions, the Cat's Eye position and the confocal position. In both positions, the defocus term of a Zernike polynomial fit is minimized for highly accurate alignment. The distance between these two positions corresponds to the radius of the spherical section, see, e.g., [15]. Note that this radius is the best-fit radius of the spherical section on the aperture that is illuminated in the confocal position. The expanded uncertainty of the radius measurement is usually in the range of a few 100 nm ($k=2$), depending on the curvature.

The sphericity (deviation from ideal sphere) can be measured with PTB's Zygo interferometer. In this setup, only the deviations from an ideal sphere (best-fit) are measured. A special alignment procedure is used, to align the surface to the confocal position, such that the illumination wavefront corresponds to the best-fit sphere of the surface and only the local deviations from this are measured. The sphericity data are given on a distinct grid that depends on the camera of the interferometer. The pointwise expanded uncertainty of the sphericity measurement is 11 nm ($k=2$). With the tilted-wave interferometer, the absolute form of the spherical section is measured, and the result can be divided into the two characteristics, the radius and the sphericity. Subsequently, the characteristics radius and sphericity can be compared to the reference measurements using a statistical evaluation. This procedure is presented in the following section.

3.3.2 Validation methods

To enable fair comparison between the TWI and the reference measurements, the comparison has to be applied on a same fixed-point grid. For this purpose, the initial measurements from both instruments must be interpolated onto the same fixed-point grid on a common surface diameter.

For comparison, the characteristics “sphericity” and “absolute radius” must be extracted from the TWI measurements. For this purpose, a best-fit sphere is calculated from the absolute form data of the TWI by using a least-squares optimization. To this end, the best-fit sphere is determined for the measurement data interpolated to a regular grid and the best-fit sphere is removed from the original data points. Interpolated data are used for the determination of the best-fit sphere because otherwise the non-regular grid of the TWI measurement would lead to different weights of different parts of the surface (e.g. for areas of more dense data points).

The result of the calculation is the radius of the best-fit sphere and the residual which corresponds to the sphericity. The corresponding uncertainties are estimated by the methods described above. Since both uncertainty evaluation approaches discussed above yield uncertainties purely for the parametric description of the form of the SUT, i.e. an uncertainty for the Zernike coefficients used in the representation, an additional Monte Carlo sampling has been performed to obtain uncertainties for the desired characteristics. In this sampling, independent and identically distributed samples are drawn from the respective distribution of the Zernike coefficients and for each realization the absolute form is calculated by adding the design form, the positioning is corrected, and the evaluation of the absolute radius and the sphericity is performed. In this sampling, independent and identically distributed samples are drawn from the respective distribution of the Zernike coefficients and for each realization the absolute form is calculated by adding the design form, the positioning is corrected, and the evaluation of the absolute radius and the sphericity is performed. The resulting sample is analyzed to obtain the standard uncertainty of the absolute radius and a point-wise standard uncertainty for the multivariate sphericity.

Furthermore, for point-wise comparison of the sphericities, correct alignment between both measurements is important. To achieve this, external and internal reference marks are often employed in practice. Otherwise, the measurements can only be aligned if there are significant manufacturing errors on the surface that can be used for this purpose, e.g. by choosing certain spatial frequencies that are suited for the alignment. Depending on the design and degrees of freedom of the reference surface and external and internal markers, different alignment steps can be performed, for further details on such methods, see e.g. [16]. It is important to note that the alignment with regard to shifts and tilts along the lateral x and y axis are only allowed to be performed with the absolute form data.

In our case, the spherical reference surface has no external or internal marks. Therefore, the only possibility to align them is by using the manufacturing errors of the surface. One method would be to use Zernike fits of both absolute measurements to determine the necessary alignment between the surfaces. To this end, the absolute form of the reference has to be calculated from the sphericity and radius measurement. Note that the alignment is only possible if the manufacturing errors are larger than the measurement errors of the instruments. To determine the alignment, the spatial frequencies that are best suited can be chosen, but the shifts and tilts (along the x and y -axis) always must be applied to the absolute form data. After alignment, the sphericity and radius can be extracted from the absolute

data.

The comparison and subsequent validation of the TWI measurement procedures can then be achieved through statistical methods. We will present here two separate comparison techniques for the two characteristics, with guidance on how to perform each method. Namely, for the example at hand, the radii are compared through observing error bars and the sphericity is validated through coverage probabilities.

3.3.3 Validation of the radius

Error bar plots provide a graphical representation of the variability of observations, and hence can serve as a good comparator between the approaches. Observing the general shape and overlap of the uncertainty bars allows one to assess the distribution of the estimated values for the radius. Confirmation of the validity of the proposed approach would be illustratively indicated by overlap between the bars of the proposal (in this example, the TWI) and the reference procedure, with each bar extending to up to two standard uncertainties either side of the estimate.

3.3.4 Validation of the sphericity

A statistic which can be used to validate a procedure is the coverage probability, which measures the proportion of measurements that lie within the uncertainty interval of a chosen procedure. To calculate the coverage probability P , one can use the following formula.

$$P = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{1}(|\theta_i^{TWI} - \theta_i^{Ref}| \leq 1.96 \times u_i)$$

Here, n is the total number of points considered, θ_i^{TWI} and θ_i^{Ref} represent the estimates obtained by the respective instruments at position i , and u_i represents the uncertainty of the chosen procedure at position i . The indicator function is equivalent to either 1 if the statement is true at i , or 0 if false. Due to the choice of 1.96 to scale the standard uncertainty u_i to an expanded uncertainty, one would typically expect the statistic P to be close to 0.95 or for the coverage calculated via the uncertainty of the virtual TWI to be similar to the coverage offered by the reference procedure. Furthermore, one can calculate the total proportion of points lying within the uncertainty interval of at least one of the procedures to assess the overlap between the coverage regions. This statistic can be obtained through the following formula.

$$P = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbb{1}(|\theta_i^{TWI} - \theta_i^{Ref}| \leq (1.96 \times u_i^{TWI} + 1.96 \times u_i^{Ref}))$$

The notation is the same as before, with additionally u_i^{TWI} and u_i^{Ref} representing the uncertainties of the TWI and reference procedures respectively.

3.4 Validation Results

3.4.1 Reference measurement of the reference specimen

To validate the VE of the TWI and the uncertainty methods developed during the ViDiT project, a highly accurate spherical reference surface with a design radius of 30 mm is measured. A photo of the surface is shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Photo of the highly accurate spherical reference surface used for the validation of the methods developed for the tilted-wave interferometer together with the coordinate system of the specimen.

The radius of this surface was measured at PTB's radius measurement bench. The result of the radius measurement on the measured diameter of 44.8 mm is

$$R = 29.99611 \text{ mm}, U(k=2) = 0.00038 \text{ mm}.$$

The sphericity of this surface was measured at PTB's Zygo interferometer. The measured sphericity is plotted in Figure 17 and stored as a point cloud. The pointwise expanded uncertainty is 11 nm ($k=2$). The diameter measured amounts to 44.8 mm.

Figure 17: Measurement result of the sphericity reference measurement.

Note that the aperture measured by the different instruments can differ. This must be considered, when comparing the results and performing the validation. To this end, the absolute form of the reference measurements was calculated by adding the form resulting from the radius measurement to the sphericity measurement using the same diameter of the sphericity and radius measurement. After this, the absolute form of the reference measurement is restricted to the aperture measured by the TWI (the largest common aperture of both TWI measurements of 33.8 mm is used here). Afterwards, the characteristics can again be extracted from the reference and from the TWI measurements by calculating the best-fit sphere (see procedure described in Section 3.1). The calculation steps for the measurements are described below in detail.

The following steps were performed for the reference measurements:

1. Calculate the absolute form on the diameter measured by the reference instruments (44.8 mm): Add the form resulting from the spherical section with the radius measured by the radius measurement to the sphericity measurement
2. Interpolate the absolute data to the common 1000 x 1000 pixel grid of the chosen evaluation diameter of 33.8 mm and restrict the original absolute data to the same diameter. Since the reference sphericity measurement

- result is given on a regular grid, the MATLAB interpolation function `interp2` with the interpolation method “cubic” is used, which is based on cubic convolution interpolation.
3. Calculate the best-fit sphere based on the interpolated data for the common evaluation diameter. The radius of the calculated best-fit sphere is the radius measurement result of the reference measurements on the common aperture.
 4. Remove the best-fit sphere from the original data points on the common evaluation diameter.
 5. Interpolate the resulting sphericity to the common regular grid (same grid used as in step no. 2). Again, the MATLAB interpolation function `interp2` with the interpolation method “cubic” is used. This is the result for the sphericity on the common aperture.
 6. Repeat the procedures 1.to 5. for $N=20000$ Monte-Carlo runs by sampling deviations to the sphericity and the radius according to the original uncertainties of the reference measurement.
 7. Calculate the standard deviation of the resulting radii and sphericities of the 20000 Monte-Carlo runs. These are the new uncertainties with $k=1$ for the reference measurements. For the sphericity, the mean value of all standard deviations of the pixels was used as the pixelwise uncertainty.

The radius of the reference measurement for the cropped surface amounts to $R = 29.99613$ mm, $U(k=2) = 380$ nm. The resulting sphericity of the reference is stored as a point cloud and is plotted in Figure 18. The pixelwise uncertainty of the sphericity amounts to $U(k=2) = 9$ nm. The uncertainty of the cropped surface was determined by performing a Monte-Carlo loop with $N=20000$ iterations for the above-mentioned steps and accounting for the uncertainties of the reference measurements “sphericity” and “radius”. From the Monte-Carlo results, the standard deviation corresponds to the uncertainty of the cropped result ($k=1$).

Figure 18: Measurement result of the sphericity measurement calculated on the diameter that was also measured by the TWI.

The reference measurement of the sphericity shows that there are only very small deviations to a best-fit sphere in the range of a few nanometer. This shows that the manufacturing quality of the reference surface is very high.

3.4.2 Measurement of the reference surface with the TWI

With the TWI, the absolute form (radius + sphericity) was measured. The

measurements were performed in two different measurement positions: One, with only a single patch (in the following called “confocal position”) and one with several patches involved, i.e. several tilted wavefronts were used for the illumination (in the following called “second position”). The results are plotted in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Measurement results of the TWI: Reconstructed absolute form for the confocal position (left) and for the second measurement position (right) on original data points.

The surface diameter measured with the TWI depends on the measurement position. In the confocal position it amounts to 36.1 mm, in the second position to 33.8 mm.

For the TWI measurements, the following steps were performed to receive the sphericities and radii on the diameter evaluated:

1. Correct coordinate system of absolute form to coordinate system of the specimen used in the reference measurements (compare Coordinate systems of Figure 14 and Figure 16).
2. Interpolate absolute data to regular grid of common surface diameter of 33.8 mm. For this purpose, the MATLAB function `scatteredInterpolant` with the interpolation method “natural” is used, which is based on nearest neighbor interpolation using a Delaunay triangulation. The triangulation is required because the TWI measurement data are usually provided on a non-equidistant grid. The `scatteredInterpolant` function is used because the TWI measurement data are usually provided on a non-equidistant grid.
3. Restrict the absolute data to the same surface diameter of 33.8 mm.
4. Calculate the best-fit sphere based on the interpolated data. The resulting radius is the radius measured by the TWI.
5. Remove the best-fit sphere from the original data points.
6. Interpolate the resulting sphericity to the common regular grid, using the same method as in 2. This is the resulting sphericity that can be compared to the reference measurement.

3.4.3 Comparison of TWI and reference

To use these data for validation of the methods developed in the project, the procedure described in section 3.2 is used. With this, the following results are obtained.

Validation of the radius

The radii for the two measurements together with the standard uncertainties of the two uncertainty evaluation approaches developed in the project are presented in

Table 2 for a surface diameter of 33.8 mm. The standard uncertainties correspond to the standard deviation. Note that only a number of key influencing factors contributed to the uncertainties.

Table 2: Radii of the two TWI measurements obtained by the two approaches and the radius of the reference measurement on the given diameter of 33.8 mm together with the standard uncertainties of the two approaches. For both approaches, the Bayesian and the LPU method, the same radius estimate has been obtained.

Instrument (Position)	Estimated radius / mm	Standard Uncertainty Bayesian approach / mm	Standard Uncertainty LPU method/ mm
TWI (Confocal)	29.99443	0.00099	0.00090
TWI (Second)	29.99387	0.00097	0.00089
Reference	29.99613		0.00019

The presented standard uncertainties for the TWI measurements in Table 2 are obtained by $N = 20000$ Monte Carlo samples and it can be seen that the uncertainty of the reference measurement is about 20% of the uncertainty obtained by the Bayesian approach. This can be explained by the input parameters considered for the TWI uncertainty approximation and their influence onto the radius results. In particular, the chosen uncertainty of the z-position of the SUT, cf. Table 1, directly translates into the radius for a measurement of a spherical surface form. The smaller the input uncertainty of the z-position of the SUT is, the smaller is the uncertainty for the radius measurement. The determination of the z-position uncertainty as well as the improvement of the z-positioning are part of current research. The assumed input uncertainty of $1 \mu\text{m}$ directly translated to the radius uncertainty.

For the validation of the radius, the error bars shown in Figure 20 were produced. It can be observed that there is some overlap between the whiskers of the approaches. As emphasized in Table 2, the main difference in the measurement results of the TWI and the reference measurement is evidently in the width of the uncertainty bands, as expected, with a much lower standard uncertainty pertaining to the reference.

Although not all sources of uncertainty are implemented in the TWI measurements and the values of the input uncertainties are only rough estimates, the measured radii for this example already match the reference within the specified uncertainties fairly well. In the TWI measurements, the radius is affected by any z-positioning difference of the SUT between the measurement setup and the model. Therefore, an alignment procedure to reduce these influences is currently developed and the input uncertainty of this positioning is investigated [17], [18]. Incorporating these additional analysis steps and uncertainty sources will, in the future, lead to an improved estimation and uncertainty evaluation. In view of the validation, it is assumed that this will also lead to better agreement in the analysed quantities.

Figure 20: Error bar plot of the radius for the two TWI positions (Confocal – Conf and second - Sec) with the two respective uncertainty evaluation methods (Bayes and LPU) and reference instrument. The black dot in the centre of the bar indicates the estimate of the radius from the respective instruments, the blue bars indicate \pm one standard uncertainty away from the estimate, and the red bar indicates \pm two standard uncertainties away from the estimate.

Validation of the sphericity

The resulting sphericities of the two TWI measurements on the surface diameter of 33.8 mm interpolated to a regular grid are plotted in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Extracted sphericities of the TWI measurements for the confocal position (left) and for the second measurement position (right). Both measurements were interpolated to a regular grid, and the best-fit sphere was calculated from interpolated data.

The sphericities measured by the TWI and the reference have not enough significant common structures to reliably align the measurements to each other. Nevertheless, the deviations of the spherical reference surface to a perfect spherical form are very small. Therefore, the measurements are still useful for validation of the VE of the TWI and the sphericities measured by the TWI mostly are caused by

the systematic measurement and model errors of the TWI.

The estimates together with the point-wise uncertainties of the sphericity obtained by both uncertainty evaluation approaches, i.e. the Bayesian approach and the LPU method are shown in Figure 22 for the confocal measurement position and in Figure 23 for the second measurement position. Note that the structure of the estimates in both approaches differ from the estimates obtained from the measurement results, since the high-frequency reconstruction is not yet included in the uncertainty approaches. The estimates obtained by the two approaches agree with each other for both positions, whereas the estimates between the two positions show slight differences. Comparing the uncertainties obtained by the two approaches shows that the uncertainties resulting from the Bayes approach are slightly larger than the ones obtained by the LPU approach and both uncertainties obtained are slightly larger for the second measurement position. This is caused by the additional inclusion of an uncertainty contribution from the model correction procedure in the Bayesian analysis. The additional input uncertainty originates from the residual of the model correction, which is small in comparison to the overall model correction error. All uncertainties for the sphericity are in the sub-nanometre range, which shows that the uncertainties are currently underestimated because some important influencing factors have not yet been taken into account. For example, although noise with a standard deviation of 10 nm was used as the input uncertainty, this is not directly transferred to the uncertainties as the reconstruction of higher frequencies is not yet included in the uncertainty estimation methods.

Figure 22: Estimates (top row) together with the point-wise uncertainties (bottom row) of the sphericity obtained by the Bayesian approach (left) and the LPU method (right) for the confocal measurement position.

Figure 23: Estimates (top row) together with the point-wise uncertainties (bottom row) of the sphericity obtained by the Bayesian approach (left) and the LPU method (right) for the second measurement position.

The coverage probabilities of the sphericity of the TWI for the respective approaches are provided in Table 3 for the Bayesian approach and in Table 4 for the LPU method. As already discussed above for the standard uncertainty, the resulting coverage offered solely by the Bayesian and the LPU method are low at both measurement positions. Therefore, uncertainty of the TWI sphericity is currently underestimated. Nevertheless, the differences between the estimate of the sphericity of the reference measurement and of the TWI measurements are in the range of only a few ten nanometer. From the coverage probabilities it can also be seen that the sphericity estimate of both approaches, Bayes and LPU, are well covered by the coverage interval obtained from the reference measurement with a coverage percentage between 82% and 94%. These results are even better when considering the total coverage, yielding coverage percentages much closer to the 95% expected from the analysis.

Table 3: Coverage probabilities, in percent, of the sphericity for the TWI at two measurement positions and of the reference for the uncertainty obtained using the Bayesian approach. The ‘Total covered’ column provides the total coverage given by both instruments at that position.

Position	Coverage (TWI uncertainty via Bayes)	Coverage (Ref. uncertainty)	Total covered (Bayes + Ref)
Confocal	17.66%	93.85%	97.22%
Second	15.20%	82.16%	91.28%

Table 4. Coverage probabilities, in percent, of the sphericity for the TWI at two measurement positions and of the reference for the LPU approach. The ‘Total covered’ column provides the total

coverage given by both instruments at that position.

Position	Coverage (TWI uncertainty via LPU)	Coverage (Ref. uncertainty)	Total covered (LPU + Ref)
Confocal	02.07%	93.08%	93.58%
Second	01.86%	82.04%	83.33%

The coverage can also be shown illustratively via Figure 24 for the Bayesian approach and via Figure 25 for the LPU method. Here, the coverage intervals have been depicted for the estimates at the line of points where the x coordinate is constant and closest to 0 mm.

Figure 24: 1D plots of the estimates taken at position x closest to 0. For the two plots on the left, the coverage interval using the TWI uncertainty calculated through the Bayesian method is provided, while with the rightmost plots, the coverage interval of the reference is illustrated. The top row shows the estimates obtained using the confocal position and the bottom row shows the estimates obtained using the second position within the TWI.

Figure 25: 1D plots of the estimates taken at position x closest to 0. For the two plots on the left, the coverage interval using the TWI uncertainty calculated through the LPU method is provided, while with the rightmost plots, the coverage interval of the reference is illustrated. The top row shows the estimates obtained using the confocal position and the bottom row shows the estimates obtained using the second position within the TWI.

Again, the deviations between the reference and the TWI measurements of a few ten nanometer are visible, which are not yet covered by the uncertainties calculated for the TWI (left). However, the uncertainties of the reference measurement (right) cover the estimates obtained by the TWI fairly well. The 1D plots show, that the uncertainty of the sphericities extracted from the TWI measurements is currently underestimated since the uncertainty budget of the TWI is not yet complete. The structure that is visible in the 1D-plots is probably mainly caused by the form deviations of the reference surfaces that were used to correct the TWI model during the model correction procedure.

3.5 Summary and Conclusions of Results

It was demonstrated in this chapter that the VE of the TWI can be validated using a reference measurement. In particular, the radius of a reference sphere was measured using PTB's radius measurement bench and its sphericity was measured using PTB's Zygo interferometer. Subsequently, the VE of the TWI and two uncertainty evaluation methods were applied to validate the VE of the TWI. The validation methods presented in this GPG can be employed to other instruments to validate VEs, especially, when instruments are used with "embedded VEs". Statistical tools, such as coverage probabilities and error bar plots, provide simple-yet-insightful metrics for assessing the distribution and variability of a proposed procedure when compared with an existing reference procedure. Provided the differentiation between the procedures is not statistically significant, the proposal can be considered valid.

While the uncertainties resulting from the TWI are rather low for the sphericity, due to the currently limited number of influencing factors included in the methods, the estimates in conjunction with the obtained uncertainties are well covered by,

and comparable to, the reference measurement and its uncertainty. Due to this agreement, the VE of the TWI is considered validated when it comes to the computation of an estimate. For a more comprehensive validation of the employed uncertainty evaluation methods, further research is required. Therefore, this validation is an important intermediate step towards reliable uncertainty evaluation for the TWI and the following aspects are subject to current and future research:

The rather low coverage probabilities of the sphericity measurements when only considering the uncertainties of the TWI can be improved, by adding the influencing parameters not yet included to the uncertainty evaluation methods. Important influencing factors that are not yet included are e.g. the higher frequency reconstruction terms, the uncertainties of the model correction procedure (as included in [12]), additional model errors caused by the form deviations of the reference surfaces used during the model correction procedure of the TWI.

Furthermore, current research also focusses on the determination of the input uncertainties, which are currently only roughly estimated.

Another way to improve the low coverage probabilities would be the use of more accurate reference surfaces during the model correction procedure (either by better manufactured ones or by including their form measured with reference techniques in the model when doing the model correction procedure) which would reduce the influence of such model errors. This is also part of future research.

Current research also focusses on the development of alignment strategies for the TWI to better align the position of the surface under test in the real experiment with the one used in the model and to determine its accuracy [17], [18]. This will also contribute to reduce the uncertainties due to alignment and will additionally enlarge the coverage probabilities / overlap of boxplots when adding the knowledge about the alignment accuracy as input uncertainties to the methods developed here. Here, especially the alignment along the optical axis (z -axis) has large impact on the radius measurement of the TWI.

3.6 Acknowledgement

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4 Validation of the virtual flow meter

4.1 The virtual flow meter

In flow metrology, VEs are used to simulate how the flow measurement is influenced by disturbed flow conditions. In this GPG, three different disturbances, namely a single elbow (SE), a double S-elbow (DSE), and a double elbow out-of-plane (DE), see Figure 26, are considered.

Figure 26: Flow disturbances considered in this GPG. Left: single elbow (SE), middle: double S-elbow (DSE), right: double elbow out-of-plane (DE). (Source: [19], CC BY 4.0).

For these configurations, an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor is calculated by means of a VE. For this, the entire physical system is modeled in a VE, applying the measurement principle to the calculated flow field. By comparing this virtually determined flow rate with the actual flow rate, an estimate of the fluid-mechanical calibration factor is provided that needs to be applied for the respective disturbed flow condition.

Of course, fluid-dynamical calibration factors can also be determined by measurements. In this case, the readings of the considered flow meter under different disturbed conditions are compared with a reference flow rate measurement. However, these measurements are costly and time-consuming as they have to be done for each specific geometry separately. In contrast, VEs allow to consider a lot of different configurations, covering a wide range of possible velocity distributions and secondary flow motions. Furthermore, the influence of uncertainties in the input parameters on the resulting prediction and uncertainty of the flow rate can be investigated systematically.

Under the assumption that the VE fully reflects the real experimental set-up and takes into account all contributions of uncertainty, its predictions can be used to correct the flow rates measured under these conditions. Only by taking the uncertainty of the VE (i.e., the uncertainty of the model) as well as the uncertainty of all influencing factors into account, one can ensure that the predictions are trustworthy. For this, the uncertainty evaluation framework introduced in [13] and [19] is extended for the flow application in such a way that all the different error and uncertainty sources are considered. Finally, the flow rate and uncertainty predicted by this approach are validated by comparison with reference measurements for specific test cases.

4.2 Uncertainty evaluation

In the ViDiT project, several methods for the uncertainty evaluation of the virtual flow meter have been considered. They are described in more detail in [13].

In this GPG, the focus is on the validation of the VE. Hence, we use only one method for uncertainty evaluation to illustrate the connection between uncertainty evaluation and validation, namely the PoD using the VE-DA combination

(PoD_VEDA), see Figure 27. This method was chosen because it uses a VE to determine the fluid dynamical calibration factor and does not require reference measurements. Furthermore, the PoD approach allows a nonlinear measurement model. In case of a linear model, an LPU method (which is also described in [13]) can be used instead. In this case, the LPU using a VE-DA combination described in [13] and [19] needs to be extended by including the simulation uncertainty in the calculation of the fluid-dynamical calibration factor.

Figure 27: Schematic overview of PoD using the VE-DA combination (PoD_VEDA). (Source: [19], CC BY 4.0).

In the following, we briefly describe the PoD_VEDA method. First, a flow case, i.e. one of the geometries illustrated in Figure 26, needs to be chosen. If a SE configuration is considered, the geometry parameters Z include the inner pipe diameter, the kinematic viscosity of the fluid, the curvature radius of the bend, the downstream distance between the disturbance and the installed flow meter, and the angular orientation of the installed flow meter. If a DSE or a DE configuration is considered, Z also includes the distance in-between the two bends. All these parameters come with uncertainties, summarized in the vector u_Z .

Furthermore, we have measurements of the path velocity X with uncertainties u_X . In a first step, samples from the following two distributions are drawn:

$$x_n \sim \mathcal{N}(X, u_x^2), z_n \sim \mathcal{N}(Z, u_z^2).$$

In each iteration, these values are then used together with an estimate of the measurand Y_0 (i.e., the flow rate) to determine the fluid-dynamical calibration factor k_n using the virtual calibration model CAVE (see [13] and [19] for details). Once, k_n is determined, y_n can be calculated using the DA.

An estimate of the measurand (i.e., the flow rate) and its uncertainty can then be determined as follows:

$$\hat{Y} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N y_n, \quad u_Y = \left(\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{n=1}^N (y_n - \hat{Y})^2 \right)^{1/2}.$$

4.3 Validation procedure

4.3.1 Errors and uncertainties

In general, the uncertainty and error sources of VEs and DTs can be divided into three categories, namely 1. errors and uncertainties in the virtual representation of the instrument, 2. errors and uncertainties in the real experiment, and 3. errors and uncertainties in the virtual representation of the measurand. In the following, we list the most relevant uncertainty and error sources for the virtual flow meter in these three categories:

1. In the FLOW application, the following errors and uncertainties may occur in the virtual representation of the instrument:
 - i. Simplified implementation of measuring principle
 - ii. Interpolation between grid points
 - iii. Approximation error of integral
2. In the FLOW application, the following errors and uncertainties may occur in the real experiment. This includes errors in the test rig, the flow meter itself and the installation of the flow meter:
 - i. Angle of installation
 - ii. Distance between the meter and the flow disturbance
 - iii. Temperature fluctuations of the water
 - iv. Uncertainty of test rig regarding the representation of the flow rate
 - v. Reproducibility of the meter (long-term stability)
 - vi. Repeatability of measurement
 - vii. Geometrical parameters (e.g., pipe diameter, bending radii, wall roughness)
3. In the FLOW application, the following errors and uncertainties may occur in the virtual representation of the measurand:
 - i. Modelling errors, especially approximation of the Navier-Stokes equations and choice of the turbulence model (CFD)
 - ii. Numerical errors
 - iii. Errors of the surrogate model substituting time-consuming simulations

The errors and uncertainties in the real experiment (listed under 2.) can directly be treated in the uncertainty evaluation framework presented in 4.2.

The errors and uncertainties in virtual representation of the instrument and the ones in the virtual representation of the measurand are often difficult to obtain separately, see [20]. One way to get an estimate of these errors and uncertainties is to validate the VE for specific configurations to obtain the so-called “simulation

uncertainty” [20]. In the following paragraph, we will determine the simulation uncertainty for the three basic disturbances SE, DSE, and DE.

In 4.3.3, it will then be explained how the uncertainty evaluation framework needs to be extended to additionally take this simulation uncertainty into account.

4.3.2 Determination of simulation uncertainty

In the following, the simulation uncertainty for the surrogate model of [21] is determined as this model is used as VE in the FLOW application. This surrogate model is based on CFD simulations calculated with the Spalart–Allmaras (SA) turbulence model [22]. The SA turbulence model is a Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) model that solves a single transport equation to calculate the effective turbulent viscosity. Its main advantages are its relative simplicity and low computational cost, making it widely used for practical engineering problems.

The simulation uncertainties are determined for the following three geometries:

1. SE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$,
2. DSE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$ and in-between distance $\frac{d_l}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 0$,
3. DE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$ and in-between distance $\frac{d_l}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 0$.

See Figure 26 for an illustration of the geometries but note that the drawings are not to scale.

Following the approach in [20], the simulation uncertainties for the geometries described above are determined as follows:

1. Calculation of the fluid-dynamical calibration factor by means of the VE (here following the notation in [20] denoted as $K_{d,S}$ as only the disturbed part is considered) for eight different downstream positions ($\frac{z}{D_{\text{pipe}}} \in \{2.45, 5.45, 10.45, 15.45, 22.49, 25.49, 30.49, 35.49\}$) and eight different installation angles ($\varphi \in \{18, 36, 63, 81, 108, 126, 153, 171\}^\circ$) for the SE and four different installation angles ($\varphi \in \{18, 63, 108, 153\}^\circ$) for the DSE and DE.
2. Comparing it with the experimentally determined fluid-dynamical calibration factor (here denoted as $K_{d,E}$) for the same parameters $\frac{z}{D_{\text{pipe}}}$ and φ .
3. Under the assumption that the measurement uncertainty is neglectable compared to the error/uncertainty of the CFD model, the difference $\delta(K_{d,S}) = K_{d,S} - K_{d,E}$ gives us the error of the simulation at the 64 (for SE) or 32 (for DSE and DE) considered measurement positions (see [20] for details).
4. Next, mean and standard deviation of the simulation error are calculated. In [20], it is checked if the mean is significant. In this case, a bias correction is performed, and the mean is shifted. However, as reference measurements are expensive and hence cannot be performed for every single geometry, the simulation error will in the following also be used for slightly different geometrical configurations (e.g. for different curvature radii or different in-between distances). Therefore, no bias correction is performed, but a larger uncertainty is used in the case that the mean is significant.
5. Calculation of the simulation uncertainty u_{sim} as follows:

$$u_{\text{sim}}^2 = u^2(K_{d,S}) = \text{mean} \left(\delta(K_{d,S}) \right)^2 + \text{std} \left(\delta(K_{d,S}) \right)^2 .$$

Figure 28: Experimentally determined fluid-dynamical calibration factors for an ultrasonic flow meter installed with different angles and at different positions downstream of the SE configuration (left), corresponding virtually determined fluid-dynamical calibration factors (middle), and resulting simulation errors of the VE.

Figure 28 illustrates the experimentally and virtually determined fluid-dynamical calibration factors for an ultrasonic flow meter installed at different angles and at different positions downstream of a SE configuration (left and middle picture). Furthermore, it shows the corresponding simulation errors for the 64 different parameters (for the SE).

The calculation procedure described above leads to the following simulation uncertainties:

1. $u_{\text{sim}} = 2.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for the SE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$,
2. $u_{\text{sim}} = 1.55 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for the DSE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$ and in-between distance $\frac{d_l}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 0$,
3. $u_{\text{sim}} = 1.98 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for the DE with curvature radius $\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 1.425$ and in-between distance $\frac{d_l}{D_{\text{pipe}}} = 0$.

4.3.3 Extension of the uncertainty evaluation framework to account for errors in the VE

In the following, the extension of the uncertainty evaluation method PoD_VEDA (see 4.2) is described, which allows the inclusion of the simulation uncertainty.

For this, we additionally draw samples $\varepsilon_n \sim \mathcal{N}(0, u_{\text{sim}}^2)$. In each iteration step, these values are then added to the virtually determined fluid-dynamical calibration factor k_n accounting for the error in the virtual calibration model CAVE, see Figure 29 for illustration.

Figure 29: Extension of the uncertainty evaluation framework to allow for errors in the VE by means of inclusion of simulation uncertainty.

The next paragraph provides step-by-step instructions on how the uncertainty evaluation framework described above can be validated. In 4.4, this procedure will then be applied to four test cases. Please note that these test cases represent realistic configurations. The exact values of some of the parameters, however, were not determined in real experiments but chosen in such a way that the procedure can be illustrated. A case study with real measurement data can be found in [23].

4.3.4 Validation procedure

To validate the VE, the following steps are performed:

1. Determine / estimate the errors and uncertainties of the real experiment (u_x and u_z).
2. Determine the simulation uncertainty u_{sim} for the respective geometrical configuration to cover the errors and uncertainties in the virtual representation of the instrument and the measurand.
3. Perform the uncertainty evaluation to determine an estimate of the measurand and its uncertainty (according to the scheme illustrated in Figure 29).
4. Check if the flow rate determined with a reference flow meter fits to the predicted flow rate incl. its uncertainty.

4.4 Validation results

In this section, we show the results for four test configurations, namely two SE and two DE configurations. The parameters of the four test cases are summarized in Table 5. Please note that the curvature radius of all configurations is $\frac{R_c}{D_{pipe}} = 1.4$, which is almost the same as in the cases, for which the simulation uncertainty has been determined in Paragraph 3.2. The in-between distance, on the other hand, which is $\frac{d_l}{D_{pipe}} = 5$ for the two DE test cases, is much larger than the one used for the calculation of the simulation uncertainty. However, as reference measurements are

expensive, they cannot be performed for a significant number of different configurations. Hence, it is a realistic case that the configuration, for which reference measurements are available to determine the simulation uncertainty, differs from the configuration, for which the uncertainty evaluation is performed. With the validation procedure performed in the following, it will be investigated whether the simulation uncertainty, which has been determined for a slightly different geometry, can be transferred to the actual flow case.

Please note that, for a better comparability between the different test cases, we use the same simulation uncertainty for all four cases, namely $u_{\text{sim}} = 2.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$.

Table 5: Parameters Z for the four configurations and corresponding uncertainties u_z (which are assumed to be the same for all test cases)

Case	Param.	D_{pipe}	ν	geo	$\frac{R_c}{D_{\text{pipe}}}$	$\frac{d_l}{D_{\text{pipe}}}$	$\frac{z}{D_{\text{pipe}}}$	α
1	Z	0.2 m	$0.89 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	SE	1.4	-	5	45°
2	Z	0.2 m	$0.89 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	SE	1.4	-	10	45°
3	Z	0.2 m	$0.89 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	DE	1.4	5	5	45°
4	Z	0.2 m	$0.89 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	DE	1.4	5	20	45°
1,2,3,4	u_z	0.001 m	$0.05 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$	-	0.1	0.1	0.1	3°

The last row in Table 5 gives the uncertainties of the input parameters. Please note that for the four test cases the same uncertainties are assumed.

Table 6 shows the measured flow rate (X), the estimate of the reference flow rate (Y_0), the predicted flow rate (\hat{Y}), its uncertainty (u_Y), and the reference flow rate (Y) in m^3/s for the four test cases. The predicted flow rate and its uncertainty have been calculated using the PoD_VEDA method described above with $N = 1000$ samples.

Table 6: Measured flow rate (X), estimate of the reference flow rate (Y_0), predicted flow rate (\hat{Y}), its uncertainty (u_Y), and reference flow rate (Y) in m^3/s for the four test cases using the PoD_VEDA method with $N = 1000$ samples.

Case	X	Y_0	\hat{Y}	u_Y	Y
1	5.706 m/s	0.1885 m^3/s	0.1888 m^3/s	0.0043 m^3/s	0.1887 m^3/s
2	0.483 m/s	0.0157 m^3/s	0.0156 m^3/s	0.0004 m^3/s	0.0158 m^3/s
3	0.477 m/s	0.0157 m^3/s	0.0161 m^3/s	0.0004 m^3/s	0.0159 m^3/s
4	5.880 m/s	0.1885 m^3/s	0.1858 m^3/s	0.0046 m^3/s	0.1887 m^3/s

In addition, the results are plotted in Figure 30. Please note that all flow rates have been scaled with the reference flow rate of the respective test case. In the left picture of Figure 30, results are plotted for the case $u_z = 0$, i.e., in the case that there are no uncertainties in the input parameters, which means that pipe diameter, viscosity, geometrical parameters, etc. are exactly known. In the right picture of Figure 30, results are plotted for the (more realistic) case that there are also uncertainties in these parameters. The corresponding values used for u_z are given in the bottom line of Table 5.

Figure 30: Flow rate and uncertainty predicted by PoD_VEDA method with $N = 1000$ samples (blue squares/green diamonds and corresponding error bars) in comparison with measured flow rates (orange dots) and reference flow rate (black line) for the four test cases described in Table 5. Left: for $u_z = 0$ (blue), right: for u_z as given in the bottom line of Table 5 (green). All flow rates have been scaled with the reference flow rate of the respective test case.

In both pictures, the orange dots show the measured flow rates (X). The blue squares and error bars are the flow rates and uncertainties predicted by the PoD_VEDA method assuming that there is no error/uncertainty in the VE. The green diamonds and error bars show the results of PoD_VEDA for the case that a simulation uncertainty of $u_{sim} = 2.25 \cdot 10^{-2}$ is used.

The results show that with the prescribed uncertainties the reference flow rate (black line in Figure 30) lies within the interval for the flow rates predicted by the PoD_VEDA method for all four test cases.

5 DT use case, part made by welding

5.1 The physical part

Welded steel structures are used widely in many applications. When welded structures are used in moving vehicles weight is minimized for practical and energy saving reasons. However, an engineering problem is how to minimize weight without compromising structural rigidity. In reality there are unintentional variations in manufacturing. There is a legend that products made on some weekdays have bad quality and lifetime shorter than expected. Although the legend is not true, disturbances may cause variations for many reasons. It is here where the concept of DT appears as useful.

The part is designed by VTT and manufactured with tolerances typical for welded structures, used in for example train wagons and forestry vehicles (Figure 31, Figure 32, Figure 33). Because the intention was to get typical welding quality the company which manufactured the part did not know that VTT would be the end user. Therefore, manufacturing was not aware of its future scientific use in the field of manufacturing quality and dimensional metrology. Reference measurements were performed using a high-precision Mitutoyo LEGEX 9106 CMM with a maximum permissible error ($E_{0,MPE}$) of $(0.55 + L/1000) \mu\text{m}$ in VTT MIKES laboratory.

Figure 31. Technical drawing of physical part.

Figure 32. Reference measurements using CMM of Case CS8 part made by welding.

5.2 DT of the part

The CAD model of the part could at first thought represent the DT. However the intention is that the DT is the representation of physical instance of one single real-world object. The DT of the part will be a skin model as a concept described in [24]. It is assumed that the part is scanned for example using fringe projection resulting in a point cloud. Based on this point cloud a STL file will be generated.

According to the concepts of Industry 4.0 in theory every manufactured part is measured and here optical methods, such a fringe projection or robotic 3D scanning using other optical sensors are promising. In this study a part typical in train wagons was selected because analysis of lifetime due to fatigue is important. This topic is also relevant for forestry vehicles Figure 33. The lifetime of each DT can now be accurately estimated by using the geometry data from the DT in a Finite Element Analysis (FEA). In this analysis it is especially misalignments of the welds of individual parts which are critical.

In [25] a topic “Digital twin for geometrical variations management” is presented and is related to the purpose of this DT. The DT contain full 3D data but it is the misalignments and angular errors between welded plates which can be regarded as measurands as these are critical for lifetime. For validation purposes these geometrical errors can be extracted from the DT and compared to measurands evaluated by reference measurements performed by tactile CMM (see Figure 32).

According to the concept of DT the complete lifetime should be covered. In our application for fatigue of welds this would require data collection of loads when the part is in use. The practical implementation of this is out of scope of this guide. Data collection of loads in a moving passenger train car or [forestry](#) vehicle is costly but on the other hand the collected data could be useful for many wear related purposes.

Figure 33 A harvester working in forest.

5.3 Validation of the DT based on measurements of ball bar and the physical part

5.3.1 Traceability from measurements of ball bar

The DT is based on measurements using fringe projection instruments used in industry. Therefore, the first uncertainty source is the measurement uncertainty of these fringe projection instruments. The standard ISO 10360-13 provides a method for verification and acceptance testing and results of such tests would be valuable. However, manufacturers of fringe projection instruments usually don't publish such data, probably because of different case specific factors (surface properties, ambient light and parameter selection during setup, calibration and measurement). One exception is the manufacturer Creaform which publish this data for some models.

In the standard ISO 10360-13 the use of several artefacts is described and the use of them all for a full verification would be too time consuming for most end users and at the stakeholder in this project it was decided to only use a ball bar.

Typically, optical CMS are able to reach measurement uncertainties in the range 0.04 mm ... 0.08 mm, when the measurement volume is about 1 m³. For verification purposes the uncertainties of the verification standard should be about 1/4 to 1/3 of the typical uncertainties of the instrument under inspection. This results in target uncertainties of the ball bar to be less than 0.01 mm ... 0.02 mm.

Obviously, the number of nominal distances from ball centre to ball centre should be as large as possible but if the number of balls is large the analysis workload also

increases. It was decided to use seven balls and the nominal length of the ball bar was fixed to 1200 mm. This is the longest length the tactile CMM at VTT MIKES can easily measure. Naturally a longer ball bar could be useful, but transportation and handling would be increasingly difficult.

A ball bar was designed and manufactured at VTT MIKES for verification of the fringe projection instruments. The ball bar has been calibrated at CMM at VTT MIKES (Figure 34).

Figure 34. Calibration of ball bar using Mitutoyo Legex CMM at VTT MIKES.

Ponsse Plc is a company in [Finland](#) that manufactures [forestry](#) vehicles such as [forwarders](#) and [harvesters](#). At Ponsse they have both Atos instrument (Figure 35) and Zeis Scanbox (Figure 36) and the ball bar was measured with these.

Figure 35. Ball bar when used for verification of an Atos instrument.

Figure 36. Ball bar when used for verification of an ScanBox 8160.

The scans are analysed by Zeiss Inspect software and the main result is distances between the balls of the ball bar and how these distances differ from reference measurements using tactile CMM. The analysis work is quite large as the ball bar is measured in different orientations. In is example of results shown for one orientation (Figure 37). It is unnecessary to show all details and results of analysis, but the conclusion was that for the measurement volume of about 1 m³ the standard deviation of the error from calibrated values was about 0.02 mm. This means roughly that the instrument is capable to measure with a measurement uncertainty of 0.04 ($k=2$).

Figure 37. Typical result of the ball bar when used for verification of an Atos ScanBox 8

instrument. The red lines represent only example of possible interpretation of measurement error.

5.3.2 Repeatability from measurements of welded part

Extensive repeatability test were performed at the Scanbox instrument with the welded part (Figure) [26]. Example of a scan is shown in figure 39 and the software Zeiss Inspect was used to evaluate geometrical positions and distances .

Figure 38. ScanBox 8160 VMR used to measure the welded part.

Figure 39. Example of one scan of the part (color code from -3 mm to 3 mm).

To get numbers for measurands from the repeatability test the following dimensional features were selected for analysis:

- Position of outermost (left and right) hole centers in x,y,z coordinates,
- position of one point, on the x-axis
- one flatness evaluation and
- one two point distance

as shown in Figure 40.

Altogether, 100 measurements were done using different options. When Zeiss Inspect is used for dimensional evaluation a large amount of different analysis options are available. In Table 7 are shown calculated standard deviations for analysis options “Gauss Full” and “Gauss Fast” in the Zeiss Inspect software.

Figure 40. Measurands on the welded part.

Table 7. Standard deviations for selected measurands using analysis options “Gauss Full” and “Gauss Fast”. Features are those noted in above figure (RHX = Right Hole X, RHY= Right Hole, Y RHZ= Right Hole Z, LHX = Left Hole X, LHY= Left Hole Y, LHZ= Left Hole Z, Pointx, Plane and Lz).

Feature	Gauss, Full and Fast n=100	Gauss, Full n=50	Gauss, Fast n=50
	/mm	/mm	/mm
RHX	0.056	0.044	0.046
RHY	0.028	0.028	0.028
RHZ	0.022	0.025	0.018
LHX	0.073	0.025	0.085
LHY	0.045	0.048	0.04
LHZ	0.028	0.031	0.018
Point X	0.01	0.006	0.011
Plane	0.116	0.061	0.135
Lz	0.035	0.031	0.039

5.4 Other errors in the DT

When 3D STL model is generated from measured point cloud mesh density is limitation for resolution. In Table 7 the gaussian full represents a denser skin model and gauss fast produces one with longer vertex edges.

Also, possible filtering and outlier removal are dependent on operator choices and might be problematic. Similarly defining elements from the data can use different methods, for example defining a circle by gaussian least squares may produce a different size or location compared to a circle created with a different definition, such as Chebyshev.

A practical issue is the optical measurement instrument not able to get data points from complete part. This can be due to unsuitable measurement angles, too few measurements, the parts structures obstructing other internal surfaces, or other similar reasons.

These are practical questions which are partly outside the scope of this report. However, results acquired at Ponsse, and especially results for repeatability reflect and contain some of these uncertainty contributions already.

5.5 Summary of validation

Welded steel structures are widely used in vehicles where weight reduction is essential for efficiency, but minimizing weight without losing rigidity is challenging.

Manufacturing variations can affect quality, making DTs valuable for managing these issues. In this case, a welded part designed by VTT was measured with high-precision CMM to establish reference data. The DT represents the actual physical part, created from optical scans like fringe projection and converted into an STL model. Using DT geometry in Finite Element Analysis enables physical instance specific lifetime predictions, for weld misalignments that impact fatigue. Optical measurement systems were verified using a calibrated ball bar, achieving uncertainties around 0.04 mm, and repeatability tests on the welded part showed deviations ranging from 0.01 mm to over 0.1 mm. Errors in DT generation can stem from mesh density, filtering, and element definition methods, while incomplete scans due to obstructed surfaces add uncertainty. Despite these challenges, results indicate that DTs combined with optical measurements can provide reliable data for structural analysis. This approach supports Industry 4.0 goals by enabling quality control and lifetime prediction for complex welded components.

6 Validation of Robotic 3D scanning system

6.1 Introduction and Objective

The purpose of this study is to validate the DT developed for the dimensional measurement system by applying the acceptance and reverification principles defined in ISO 10360-13:2021, Part 13: Optical 3D scanning systems, Acceptance and reverification tests (see Figure 41). The validation aims to assess whether the DT correctly reproduces the metrological behaviour of the physical system under realistic operating conditions, including repeatability, stability over time and sensitivity to environmental and instrumental error sources.

A dedicated multi-sphere artefact was used as the reference standard for this validation. The artefact consists of five precision spheres, mounted along a rigid bar and equally spaced over a total length of approximately 1 m, providing well-defined geometrical features suitable for traceable verification. The nominal inter-centre distances were previously calibrated using a laser tracker, ensuring traceability to the SI metre and providing the reference values required for comparison between physical measurements and simulated data.

The DT replicates the complete measurement process, including sensor characteristics, environmental influences, and the geometric model of the artefact. By comparing the DT output with experimental measurements of the sphere bar, the study evaluates the capability of the DT to predict measurement results and associated uncertainties. This approach follows the broader methodology described in previous sections of this deliverable, where validation relies on statistical consistency between reference data and virtual measurements.

A long-duration measurement campaign was carried out to test the DT under conditions representative of industrial operation. The analysis presented in the following sections includes the description of the artefact and experimental setup, the measurement strategy, the modelling approach implemented in the DT, and a detailed comparison between experimental and simulated results. Finally, the validation is assessed within the framework of ISO 10360-13.

Figure 41. Lay out proposed by ISO10360 -13 part3. Scale bar

6.2 Artefact and Experimental Setup

The validation experiments were carried out using a custom multi-sphere artefact

designed to provide stable and traceable geometrical references. The artefact consists of five precision scanning spheres mounted on a carbon-fibre bar of approximately 1 m in total length. Carbon fibre was selected due to its low thermal expansion coefficient and high rigidity, ensuring minimal deformation during long-duration testing. The spheres are specifically manufactured for optical scanning applications, featuring a surface treatment that minimizes reflections and provides uniform response for optical triangulation sensors.

Figure 42

The nominal inter-centre distances were established prior to the experiment using a laser tracker whose calibration status and measurement performance were verified according to its corresponding acceptance and verification procedures. This ensured that all measured distances were traceable to the SI metre (see Figure 42). The resulting calibrated distances were then adopted as the reference values for all comparisons between the physical measurements and the DT simulations.

Figure 42. Laser tracker measuring the scale bar

All measurements were performed under controlled environmental conditions, ensuring stable temperature and lighting throughout the 48-hour campaign. The artefact was rigidly fixed during the entire experiment to avoid repositioning effects, while the sensor was moved by a Stäubli TX90L robot.

The measurement system consisted of a Gocator line-triangulation sensor, which acquires 3D data by projecting a laser line onto the artefact and reconstructing surface geometry from the reflected profile. For each acquisition, the spherical features were reconstructed by applying a least-squares sphere fitting to the acquired point cloud. To improve robustness, the fitting routine included an outlier rejection step, removing the top 5% of points with the largest fitting residuals.

This configuration, rigid artefact, controlled environment, robot-mounted triangulation sensor and traceable calibration of nominal values, provides a well-defined metrological framework for evaluating the agreement between real measurements and the DT.

6.3 Measurement Strategy and Data Acquisition

A long-duration measurement campaign was conducted to evaluate the behaviour of the physical system under stable but realistic operating conditions and to provide a robust dataset for comparison with the DT. The complete experiment spanned **48 hours**, during which the system acquired a total of **2000 measurements** of the five-

sphere artefact. The measurements were collected at a **constant and uniform rate** over the entire duration of the campaign.

All measurements were performed following the same programmed robot trajectory, ensuring consistent execution of the measurement process. By maintaining identical motion and sensor positioning conditions, the experiment captures the combined behaviour of the entire measurement chain: robot, calibration, and triangulation sensor. Any variability detected in the resulting inter-centre distances therefore reflects the intrinsic performance of the full system rather than changes in the measurement procedure. The artefact remained rigidly fixed throughout the campaign. A system calibration was performed during the test campaign, following standard operating procedures, but no further intervention was carried out during the remaining measurement period (see Figure 43).

For each acquisition, a point cloud of the five spheres was obtained using the line-triangulation Gocator sensor. A least-squares sphere fitting routine was applied to each dataset, incorporating a 5% outlier rejection criterion to ensure robust feature reconstruction. Based on the fitted sphere centres, the primary measurands were defined as the inter-centre distances from the first sphere to each of the remaining four spheres. These distances provide a set of redundant but sensitive indicators of system performance, enabling the identification of both repeatability characteristics and potential systematic effects present in the measurements.

No temporal filtering or smoothing was applied. Each measurement was processed independently to preserve the intrinsic variability of the system and to allow a direct comparison with the DT simulations. The resulting dataset forms a consistent and traceable basis for assessing the agreement between physical measurements and the DT model, as described in the following sections.

Figure 43. Example of the measurement process

6.4 DT Modelling

The DT reproduces the complete measurement process of the robot–sensor system, integrating the behaviour of both components as characterised in [27]. These previous studies provided quantitative estimates of systematic and random errors in the Stäubli TX90L robot and in the Gocator line-triangulation sensor, which are directly embedded in the DT as calibrated error sources (see Figure 44).

The DT includes an idealised geometric model of the five-sphere artefact, using the laser-tracker-calibrated inter-centre distances as the nominal reference. Based on this geometry, the DT generates synthetic point clouds that mimic the sampling pattern of the Gocator sensor when mounted on the robot.

Each simulated dataset is processed using the same workflow as the real measurements, including least-squares sphere fitting and 5% outlier rejection, ensuring direct comparability between experimental and virtual sphere-centre estimates.

Systematic effects, such as stable robot positioning offsets and repeatable sensor reconstruction deviations, are applied uniformly across all simulations. Random effects, including robot repeatability and optical noise, are generated for each virtual measurement according to the statistical distributions obtained from the earlier characterisations.

By combining nominal geometry with realistic systematic and random disturbances, the DT produces virtual measurements that reflect the behaviour of the physical system over time, enabling a meaningful comparison with the 48-hour experimental dataset.

Figure 44. Virtual representation of the test

6.5 Experiment–Simulation Comparison

A comprehensive comparison was carried out between the 2000 experimental measurements obtained over the 48-hour campaign and the corresponding virtual measurements generated by the DT. The objective was to assess the extent to which

the DT reproduces the statistical behaviour of the real system, with particular attention to the distribution of the measurands and the presence of systematic effects.

For each measurement, the four inter-centre distances defined from sphere 1 to the remaining spheres were evaluated. The experimental dataset shows a stable and repeatable behaviour, with standard deviations in the range of 0.0068–0.0117 mm. The DT reproduces the same qualitative trend, although the simulated variability is consistently higher, with standard deviations between 0.0147–0.0175 mm. This indicates that the DT captures the general magnitude and ordering of the observed variability but tends to generate slightly broader distributions than those measured in practice.

When comparing the central tendency of the distributions, both the real and simulated datasets show consistent mean values for each measurand, although residual offsets are present. These offsets are not large, but they persist throughout the full dataset and therefore indicate the presence of systematic effects in the real measurement chain. The DT incorporates a partial model of these systematic components, derived from earlier characterisation of the robot and the sensor; however, the magnitude and direction of the experimental offsets are not reproduced exactly. As a result, the DT captures the general pattern of the systematic deviations, but not their full extent. This behaviour is consistent with the fact that some of the systematic mechanisms observed in the 48-hour experiment—particularly those related to the combined interaction of calibration, robot positioning and sensor reconstruction—are only partially represented in the current DT implementation.

The comparison of the distributions reveals similar behaviour. The shape of the simulated histograms resembles that of the experimental data, and no multimodal or irregular patterns are observed in either case. The DT successfully reproduces the overall structure of the statistical distributions, although with a slightly wider spread. This reflects the tendency of the DT to include a conservative level of random disturbance, whereas the real system exhibits somewhat lower measurement noise under the controlled conditions of the experiment.

No temporal filtering was applied, and the analysis of the measurement sequence confirms a generally stable temporal behaviour in both datasets. The DT does not introduce artificial trends or discontinuities, and the experimental measurements do not show evident drift over the 48 hours. Differences between simulation and experiment therefore arise mainly from the relative magnitude of random variability and the incomplete representation of systematic effects.

In summary, the comparison indicates that the DT reproduces the overall statistical behaviour of the real measurement system, including the qualitative structure of the distributions and the ordering of the measurands. Differences appear primarily in the magnitude of the variability, slightly higher in the simulation, and in the partial representation of systematic deviations, which are present in the experimental data but not fully captured by the DT. These observations provide a basis for future refinement of the DT error models while confirming that the current implementation offers a coherent and realistic approximation of the system's behaviour.

Simulations

(mm)	1-2	1-3	1-4	1-5
Nominal	238.953	475.972	713.793	956.691
Mean	238.953	475.973	713.793	956.698
Standard deviation	0.0156	0.0147	0.0160	0.0175
Nominal-Mean	-0.000	-0.000	-0.001	-0.006

Experiment

(mm)	1-2	1-3	1-4	1-5
Nominal	238.953	475.972	713.793	956.691
Mean	238.990	476.082	713.829	956.700
Standard deviation	0.0085	0.0068	0.0092	0.0117
Nominal-Mean	-0.037	-0.110	-0.036	-0.009

6.6 Conclusion of the Robotic 3D scanning system

This study has presented a validation exercise of the DT for the robot-mounted optical measurement system using a five-sphere artefact measured over a 48-hour period. The comparison between the experimental dataset and the simulated measurements shows that the DT reproduces the general statistical behaviour of the system, particularly in terms of the relative magnitude and ordering of the inter-centre distances.

The experimental results demonstrate stable and consistent performance of the measurement chain, with lower variability than that predicted by the DT. The DT generates broader distributions, reflecting its more conservative modelling of random disturbances. Systematic effects were observed in the real measurements, and although the DT includes a representation of these components, it does not reproduce their full magnitude. As a result, the DT aligns with the overall trends but does not capture all persistent offsets present in the physical system.

Despite these differences, the DT provides a coherent approximation of the system behaviour under controlled conditions and constitutes a useful basis for further development. The comparison highlights areas where the DT can be refined, especially in the representation of systematic mechanisms within the robot-sensor chain. Continued alignment of the DT with empirical results is expected to improve its predictive accuracy and strengthen its role as a complementary tool for analysing and understanding the performance of the measurement system.

7 Validation of the reference rotary table DT

This work proposes a validation of the DT framework for angular error compensation of a high-precision rotary table. The proposed approach relies on the continuous interaction between the physical rotary table and its virtual entity. The physical system provides real-time measurements from multiple sensors; dual encoder, thermal probes, and capacitive sensors, which reflect the actual state of the system during operation.

These measurements are assimilated through a particle-filter-based data assimilation module, which enables the fusion of sensor information while accounting for uncertainties and non-linear system behavior. Within this framework, a virtual rotary table is continuously updated and implants three complementary models: a geometrical error model, a thermal drift model, and sensor error models representing measurement noise, bias, and imperfections.

By synchronizing the virtual model with the physical system through data assimilation, the DT provides an estimate of the true angular position and delivers a corrected angle in real time. This corrected angle can be used either for metrological evaluation or for fed back into the control loop, leading to enhanced accuracy, robustness, and traceability of angular measurements over a wide range of operating conditions.

7.1 Geometrical model

7.1.1 Projection process of SDT (Small Displacement Torsor)

Figure 45. Mounted capacitive sensors

For eight operational capacitive sensors each capacitive sensor is defined by its position in space

$$p_i = \begin{pmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ z_i \end{pmatrix}_{i \in [1...5]}$$

And its measuring direction $n_i = \begin{pmatrix} n_{xi} \\ n_{yi} \\ n_{zi} \end{pmatrix}_{i \in [1...5]}$.

The measured displacement by each capacitive sensor is expressed this way:

$$\delta_i = n_i^T (T(\theta) + R(\theta) \times r_i) \quad (1)$$

Where $T = [T_x \ T_y \ T_z]$ and $R = [R_x \ R_y \ R_z]$ and θ is the measured position angle

$$H_i = (n_{xi} \ n_{yi} \ n_{zi} \ y_i n_{zi} - n_{yi} z_i \ z_i n_{xi} - n_{zi} x_i \ x_i n_{yi} - y_i n_{xi})$$

$$u = [T_x \ T_y \ T_z \ R_x \ R_y \ R_z]$$

Where H_i represents a line from the configuration matrix $H \in \mathbf{R}^{8 \times 6}$

Expanding (1) to all sensors

$$\delta = Hu \quad (2)$$

In order to solve the equation (2) we use least squares by:

Minimizing the cost function $J(u) = (\delta - Hu)^T (\delta - Hu)$ (3)

The derivative of (3) gives $\hat{u} = (H^T H)^{-1} H^T \delta$ (4)

\hat{u} Gives you the best fit of translations and rotations that reproduces the measured displacements.

→ Solving LS using SVD (singular values decomposition) so that: $\hat{u} = V_{svd} \left(\frac{M}{U_{svd}} * \delta \right)$

Where $H = U_{svd} S V_{svd}$

7.1.2 Geometrical error

$$E_{\text{geo}}(\theta_i) = \frac{T_x}{R} \cos\theta_i + \frac{T_y}{R} \sin\theta_i + \beta_x R_x \cos(2\theta_i) + \beta_y R_y \sin(2\theta_i) + \gamma T_z \quad (6)$$

This model describes the angular signature of the geometric as a function of the angular position θ_i . It decomposes the error into harmonic contributions associated with radial runout, tilt, and axial motion.

$\frac{T_x}{R} \cos\theta_i$, $\frac{T_y}{R} \sin\theta_i$ are associated with the translational components (T_x, T_y) of the small-displacement torsor, which represent the radial runout of the table. For a given (T_x, T_y), the division by the radius R shows that the same lateral translation generates a smaller angular deviation at larger radii. Physically, these 1/rev harmonics correspond to an eccentricity of the rotation axis, leading to a sinusoidal error with one cycle per revolution.

$\beta_x R_x \cos(2\theta_i)$, $\beta_y R_y \sin(2\theta_i)$ are associated with the rotational components (R_x, R_y), which describe small tilts of the rotary table about orthogonal axes. The coefficients β_x and β_y are sensitivity factors determined by the geometry and orientation of the capacitive sensors. These contributions give rise to 2/rev harmonics, characteristic of a rocking motion of the table, and are interpreted as signatures of angular misalignment or tilt of the spindle relative to the reference axis.

γT_z represents the axial translation T_z of the table. For radial capacitive sensors, the corresponding sensitivity factor γ is close to zero, indicating that pure axial motion has a negligible effect on the measured radial displacement. In practice, this component can often be ignored in the reconstruction of radial geometric errors.

Figure 46. Geometrical error variation

7.2 Thermal drift model

7.2.1 Proxies based model

$$\Delta\theta_{\text{stat}} = k_0 + k_U \cdot U + k_{G1} \cdot G_1 + k_{G2} \cdot G_2 \quad (7)$$

where:

- k_0 = constant angular offset (μrad)
- $U = T - T_{\text{ref}}$ = uniform thermal expansion proxy (difference from reference

temperature, °C)

- $G_1 = \frac{dT}{dt}$ = rate of temperature change (°C/s) captures transient gradient effects
- $G_2 = H(T) =$ thermal imbalance function
- $k_U, k_{G1}, k_{G2} =$ identified sensitivities ($\mu\text{rad}/^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu\text{rad}/(^\circ\text{C}/\text{s})$, $\mu\text{rad}/^\circ\text{C}$ respectively)

Proxies	Physical signification
U	Direct proportional expansion. When the entire table heats uniformly, all materials expand.
G_1	Rate-of-change sensitivity. Motors, bearings, and electronics generate transient heat.
G_2	Unequal gradients between structure and metrological loop cause tilt/bending

7.2.2 Results and interpretation

Figure 47: Thermal proxies

The Figure 47 illustrates the temporal evolution of three thermal proxies derived from the temperature measurement T_1 : the temperature deviation $U = T_1 - T_{\text{ref}}$, its time derivative $G_1 = dT/dt$, and the high-pass filtered component $G_2 = \text{HP}(T_1)$. The temperature deviation U exhibits slow and bounded variations, with amplitudes typically confined within ± 0.05 . An initial heating phase is observed during the first 400–500 s, where U increases progressively up to approximately +0.09. This is followed by a gradual cooling phase reaching approximately -0.05 between 1200 s and 1500 s. A secondary, lower-amplitude thermal cycle appears after 2400 s. The small amplitude and long characteristic time of these variations indicate that the thermal behavior is primarily affected by slow internal heat generation and conductive transfer, rather than by rapid environmental perturbations.

The time derivative $G_1 = dT/dt$ remains close to zero throughout most of the acquisition, with only small transient peaks occurring during transitions between the heating and cooling phases. This confirms that the system operates under quasi-static thermal conditions.

The high-pass filtered component $G_2 = HP(T_1)$ isolates the fast thermal fluctuations. Its amplitude remains negligible compared to U , and no persistent high-frequency oscillations are observed.

Figure 48: Thermal drift error

Figure 48 compares the measured thermal angle error $\Delta\Theta$ with the predictions of the static and dynamic thermal models.

7.3 Virtual dual encoder

The objective of the virtual dual-encoder simulation is to numerically reproduce the behavior of the Dual encoder (Figure 49) that is the main measuring system of LNE's reference rotary table.

The model simulate the complete measurement sequence: continuous rotation of a common shaft, independent readings from two encoders, superposition of physical error sources, and numerical integration of the differential signal over one revolution.

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The model simulate the complete measurement sequence: continuous rotation of a common shaft, independent readings from two encoders, superposition of physical error sources, and numerical integration of the differential signal over one revolution.

Figure 49: Dual encoder

The encoder disks are assumed to rotate at constant angular speed ω driven by a motor:

$$\omega = \frac{360 n_{\text{rpm}}}{60} \text{ [deg/s]} \quad (8)$$

where n_{rpm} is the rotational speed in revolutions per minute. The revolution period is

$$T_{\text{rev}} = \frac{60}{n_{\text{rpm}}} \quad (9)$$

One revolution is sampled at N_s samples per turn. The nominal sampling period is

$$\Delta t_0 = \frac{T_{\text{rev}}}{N_s} \quad (10)$$

To reproduce realistic acquisition conditions, a random sampling jitter is added:

$$\Delta t_i = \Delta t_0 + \varepsilon_i, \quad \varepsilon_i \sim \mathcal{U}(-0.1\Delta t_0, 0.1\Delta t_0).$$

The cumulative time instants follow

$$t_i = \sum_{k=1}^i \Delta t_k, \quad i = 1, \dots, N_s.$$

Three dominant error sources, affect each encoder output: graduation errors, eccentricity errors, and interpolation errors.

7.4 Dual encoder error sources

7.4.1 Graduations errors

Division errors result from imperfections in the scale graduation and are modeled as a repeatable periodic function over one revolution:

$$E_{\text{div}}(\theta) = A_{\text{div}} \sin\left(2\pi f_{\text{div}} \frac{\theta}{360^\circ} + \phi_{\text{div}}\right) \quad (11)$$

Here A_{div} is the amplitude, f_{div} the spatial frequency, and ϕ_{div} the phase. Graduation error is assumed to be stable in time, periodic with period 360° , and zero-mean over $[0, 360^\circ]$.

Eccentricity

Radial eccentricity between the disk center and the true axis of rotation generates a first-harmonic angular error.

$$E_{ecc}(\theta) = A_{ecc} \cos\left(2\pi \frac{\theta}{360^\circ} + \phi_{ecc}\right) \quad (12)$$

For small eccentricity e and mean graduation radius R , the amplitude can be approximated as

$$A_{ecc} \approx \frac{2e}{R} \quad (13)$$

7.4.2 Interpolation error

Interpolation error arises from non-ideal electronic interpolation of sinusoidal encoder signals. It is modeled as a high-frequency periodic function within a single pitch p .

$$E_{interp}(\theta) = A_{interp} \sin(2\pi N_{interp} \xi(\theta) + \phi_{interp}) \quad (14)$$

with the local normalized coordinate

$$\xi(\theta) = \frac{\theta \bmod p}{p} \quad (15)$$

7.4.3 Virtual measurement

The fixed encoder measurement is modeled as the sum of the true angle and its errors:

$$\theta_{Fixed}(\theta_{true}) = \theta_{true} + E_{div,1}(\theta_{true}) + E_{ecc,1}(\theta_{true}) + E_{interp,1}(\theta_{true}) \quad (16)$$

The mobile encode is mounted on the rotating table and therefore measures the true shaft angle shifted by a nominal offset α :

$$\theta_{mobile}(\theta_{true}) = (\theta_{true} + \alpha) + E_{div,2}(\theta_{true} + \alpha) + E_{ecc,2}(\theta_{true} + \alpha) + E_{interp,2}(\theta_{true} + \alpha) \quad (17)$$

The observation of the dual encoder is the angular difference

$$\Delta(\theta_{true}) = \theta_{Mobile}(\theta_{true}) - \theta_{Fixed}(\theta_{true}) \quad (18)$$

This can be written as

$$\Delta(\theta_{true}) = \alpha + \Delta E(\theta_{true}) \quad (19)$$

with the differential error

$$\Delta E(\theta_{true}) = [E_{div,2} - E_{div,1}] + [E_{ecc,2} - E_{ecc,1}] + [E_{interp,2} - E_{interp,1}] \quad (20)$$

The true shaft angle θ_{true} has been eliminated by construction ; only the nominal offset α and residual error terms remain.

Each error term is modeled as periodic over one revolution. Consequently, the combined differential error $\Delta E(\theta)$ is also periodic.

$$\int_0^{360^\circ} \Delta E(\theta) d\theta = 0 \quad (21)$$

The estimated offset $\hat{\alpha}$ is defined as the spatial average of the differential signal over one full revolution:

$$\hat{\alpha} = \frac{1}{360^\circ} \int_0^{360^\circ} \Delta(\theta) d\theta \quad (22)$$

Using (21),

$$\hat{\alpha} = \alpha + \frac{1}{360^\circ} \int_0^{360^\circ} \Delta E(\theta) d\theta \quad (23)$$

With the zero-mean equation (23),

$$\hat{\alpha} = \alpha \quad (24)$$

In the simulation, only discrete samples $\Delta_i = \Delta(\theta_i)$ at non-uniform angles $\theta_i = \theta_{\text{true}}(t_i)$ are available. The integral is approximated by a trapezoidal rule after sorting the samples by increasing θ_i :

$$\hat{\alpha} \approx \frac{1}{360^\circ} \sum_{i=1}^{N_s-1} \frac{\Delta_i + \Delta_{i+1}}{2} (\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i) \quad (25)$$

This formulation remains valid for non-uniform angular steps, if the ordering in θ is respected.

Figure 50. Dual encoder simulation

The Figure 50 shows the results of the virtual dual encoder and the table below explains the difference between the nominal requested angle and the virtually estimated one.

Table 8. Difference between the nominal requested angle and the virtually estimated angle.

Nominal angle (Ideal)	Virtual measured angle
0	0.0000098°
15	14.9999992°
30	29.9999970°

45	44.9999945°

7.5 Particle filtering

7.5.1 State vector and dynamical model

Within the DT framework, the particle filter operates on a state that combines the angle with the main model parameters. At discrete time step k , the state vector is defined as

$$\mathbf{x}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \theta_k \\ \mathbf{u}_k \\ \mathbf{k}_{\text{th},k} \\ \boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{enc},k} \end{bmatrix}$$

where θ_k is the rotary table angle, $\mathbf{u}_k = [T_x, T_y, T_z, R_x, R_y, R_z]^T$ is the SDT, $\mathbf{k}_{\text{th},k} = [k_0, k_U, k_{G1}, k_{G2}]^T$ and the thermal sensitivities of the proxy-based drift model, and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{enc},k}$ groups the dual encoder parameters.

The evolution of the state is described by a stochastic transition model

$$\mathbf{x}_k = f(\mathbf{x}_{k-1}, u_k) + \mathbf{w}_k \quad (26)$$

where u_k is the nominal angle, f propagates θ_k according to the evolution model and applies slow random walks to \mathbf{u}_k , $\mathbf{k}_{\text{th},k}$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{enc},k}$, and \mathbf{w}_k is a zero-mean process noise accounting for unmodelled dynamics.

7.5.2 Virtual encoder observation model

For a given state \mathbf{x}_k , the virtual dual encoder inserted in the DT generates a synthetic waveform over one revolution:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}}_k = \mathcal{E}(\theta_k, \mathbf{u}_k, \mathbf{k}_{\text{th},k}, \boldsymbol{\eta}_{\text{enc},k}; U(t), G_1(t), G_2(t)) \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

where \mathcal{E} combines the geometrical error, the static thermal drift and the dual encoder error models described in the VE. The measured waveform at time step k is

$$\mathbf{s}_k^{\text{obs}} = \hat{\mathbf{s}}_k + \mathbf{v}_k \quad (27)$$

with \mathbf{v}_k representing encoder noise and residual modelling errors.

The Bayesian filtering problem consists in estimating the posterior density

$$p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{s}_{1:k}^{\text{obs}})$$

where $\mathbf{s}_{1:k}^{\text{obs}} = \{\mathbf{s}_1^{\text{obs}}, \dots, \mathbf{s}_k^{\text{obs}}\}$. This density is approximated by a set of N_p weighted particles:

$$p(\mathbf{x}_k | \mathbf{s}_{1:k}^{\text{obs}}) \approx \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} w_k^{(i)} \delta(\mathbf{x}_k - \mathbf{x}_k^{(i)}) \quad (28)$$

With $\{\mathbf{x}_k^{(i)}, w_k^{(i)}\}_{i=1}^{N_p}$ updated recursively.

7.5.3 Waveform-based similarity criterion

Classical particle filters define the likelihood from pointwise residuals between measured and predicted observations. In contrast, the proposed R²Filtre evaluates

the coherence of the full dual encoder waveform.

$$\mathbf{s}_k^{\text{obs}} = [s_{k,1}^{\text{obs}}, \dots, s_{k,N}^{\text{obs}}]^T, \quad \hat{\mathbf{s}}_k^{(i)} = [\hat{s}_{k,1}^{(i)}, \dots, \hat{s}_{k,N}^{(i)}]^T$$

Represent the observed and virtual waveforms associated with particle i . The sample mean of the observed waveform is

$$\bar{s}_k^{\text{obs}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N s_{k,j}^{\text{obs}} \quad (29)$$

the total sum of squares is

$$SS_{\text{tot},k} = \sum_{j=1}^N (s_{k,j}^{\text{obs}} - \bar{s}_k^{\text{obs}})^2 \quad (30)$$

and the residual sum of squares for particle i is

$$SS_{\text{res},k}^{(i)} = \sum_{j=1}^N (s_{k,j}^{\text{obs}} - \hat{s}_{k,j}^{(i)})^2 \quad (31)$$

The waveform-based coefficient of determination is then defined as

$$R_{k,i}^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_{\text{res},k}^{(i)}}{SS_{\text{tot},k}} \quad (32)$$

A value $R_{k,i}^2$ close to 1 indicates that the triplet $(E_{\text{geo}}, \Delta\theta_{\text{stat}}, \text{encoder model})$ associated with particle i explains almost all of the variance of the measured waveform, whereas $R_{k,i}^2 \leq 0$ corresponds to a model performing less significant than the constant predictor \bar{s}_k^{obs} .

7.5.4 R² based likelihood and weight update

The R² Filtre introduces a pseudo-likelihood that depends exclusively on the waveform-based coherence quantified by $R_{k,i}^2$. It is defined as

$$\mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_k^{(i)}) = p(\mathbf{s}_k^{\text{obs}} | \mathbf{x}_k^{(i)}) \propto \exp(\alpha R_{k,i}^2) \quad (33)$$

where $\alpha > 0$ is a tunable selectivity gain. Large values of α strongly penalise particles whose virtual waveform is poorly correlated with the observation, whereas smaller values yield a more permissive weighting of particles.

In the sequential importance-sampling framework, the unnormalised weights are updated according to

$$\tilde{w}_k^{(i)} = w_{k-1}^{(i)} \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{x}_k^{(i)}) = w_{k-1}^{(i)} \exp(\alpha R_{k,i}^2) \quad (34)$$

and then normalized as

$$w_k^{(i)} = \frac{\tilde{w}_k^{(i)}}{\sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \tilde{w}_k^{(j)}} \quad (35)$$

The effective sample size is

$$N_{\text{eff},k} = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^{N_p} (w_k^{(i)})^2} \quad (36)$$

and, whenever $N_{\text{eff},k}$ falls below a prescribed threshold, a resampling step (for example, systematic or stratified) is performed to limit weight degeneracy and concentrate particles around the most coherent waveform reconstructions.

At each time step, the new particles are obtained as ensemble statistics over the posterior particle set. The thermally corrected angular estimate is given by the weighted mean

$$\hat{\theta}_k = \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} w_k^{(i)} \theta_k^{(i)} \quad (37)$$

The R^2 Filtre provides a corrected angle $\hat{\theta}_k$, and it acts as a model-consistency filter that accepts or rejects candidate geometrical, thermal and sensor models according to their ability to reconstruct the full measurement waveform.

Nominal Angle (°)	Residual Error (")
360	+0.010"
345	+0.012"
330	+0.010"
315	+0.010"
300	-0.010"
285	-0.008"
270	-0.020"

The residual angular errors obtained after particle filter correction remain within a very narrow range of approximately ± 0.02 arcseconds, demonstrating a high level of consistency across all evaluated angular positions. The distribution of errors is nearly symmetric around zero, indicating the absence of significant systematic bias in the estimation process.

The slight variations observed between angles are minimal and do not exhibit any strong periodic or position-dependent behavior, suggesting that the dominant geometric and thermal error components have been effectively compensated. The maximum residual ($-0.020''$ at 270°) remains within the same order of magnitude as the overall residual dispersion, confirming stable filter performance.

Overall, these results validate the effectiveness of the R^2 -based particle filter in reducing angular measurement errors to the sub- $0.02''$ level, which is consistent with the closure error metrics reported for the full digital twin. This demonstrates that the filtering approach provides robust and repeatable correction capability for high-precision angular metrology applications.

8 Nanoindentation DT – Validation

Nanoindentation consists of applying a force F by means of a calibrated indenter with a known geometry to sample whose mechanical surface properties are the measurand. During the test, the applied force and the indenter penetration in the sample, h , are measured, resulting in an indentation curve (IC), i.e., $F(h)$, example is shown in Figure 51. The force is typically applied with a loading-holding-unloading cycle [28, 29]. Nanoindentation allows high spatial resolution mechanical characterisation of the mechanical properties of a surface, e.g., in terms of young modulus, hardness.

Figure 51 Annotation of critical IC points for continuity: 0: first contact point, 1: end of loading and beginning of primary holding, 2: end of primary holding and start of unloading, 3: end of unloading and start of secondary holding, 4: end of secondary holding.

8.1 DT modelling

DT of nanoindentation was developed relying on a material-based approach. The Physical to Virtual (P2V) twinning was established modelling each portion of the indentation cycle by means of a nonlinear orthogonal distance regression (ODR), with the mathematical model selected based on contact mechanics theory. Further details are available in D2 [27]. Relevantly, each portion of the indentation is independently modelled, ensuring continuity such that:

$$F = f(h; \boldsymbol{\beta}) \quad (10.1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ are the parameters of the virtual entity estimated by ODR.

The DT aims at performing automated quality control of the nanoindentation while being capable of detecting most common error sources, e.g., shown in Figure 52.

Figure 52. Typical measurement errors in nanoindentation. (a) “nose” due to too short holding: blue, loading; red, unloading with nose; green, primary holding and unloading with correct shape. (b) thermal drift: notice the slope in the secondary holding of $h(t)$;

In particular, with reference to Figure 51, the following quality controls are implemented:

- $h_{max}(=h_2) > h_{0,holding}(=h_1)$, if such condition is not met, typically it is due to a poor indenter mounting
- $\left. \frac{dh}{dt} \right|_{holding_2} = 0$, otherwise a significant thermal drift is present
- $S_m = \left. \frac{dF}{dh} \right|_{h=h_{max}(=h_2)} > 0$, otherwise a “nose” is present indicating an insufficient duration of the primary holding which did not compensate the room-temperature creep
- $M = M_{train}$, i.e., the mechanical characteristics are statistically not different from the expected material response. The considered mechanical characteristics are: S_m, S, E_{IT}, H_{IT} . Systematic differences may indicate a change in either the shape of the indenter, due to wear, if the sample is a certified reference material, or a change in the sample material composition, for industrial applications.
- $s(\varepsilon_F) = s(\varepsilon_F)_{train}$, i.e., the standard deviation of the fitting residuals, filtered to exclude long wavelengths due to empirical deviation from theoretical ideal assumption of contact mechanics, are not statistically different from the training. Residual standard deviations is associated with the noise content of the measurement: an increase, particularly, may indicate a change in environmental conditions.
- $s(E_{IT}) = s(E_{IT})_{train}$, i.e. the reproducibility of the evaluated indentation modulus is not statistically different from the quantity evaluated during training, i.e. the P2V twinning. This condition allows monitoring if surface integrity of the sample under test has changed significantly.
- $\beta = \beta_{train}$, allowing to control if the shape of the indentation curve has changed significantly, which may happen due to unexpected response of the material, e.g., different material composition, cracking, phase transformation, etc., or because of indenter tip wear-out.

Quality controls are performed for cases (a) to (d) implementing Welch's t-test, a test statistic t

$$t = \frac{X_{test} - X_{train}}{\sqrt{u_{X_{test}}^2 + u_{X_{train}}^2}} \quad (10.2)$$

$$u_{M_{train}}^2 = u_{GUM_{train}}^2 + u_{reproducibility}^2 \quad (10.3)$$

$$u_{M_{test}}^2 = u_{GUM_{test}}^2 \quad (10.4)$$

In particular, X_{test} is the quantity to be controlled, e.g., for case (a) $h_{max} - h_{0,holding}$, for case (b) $\left. \frac{dh}{dt} \right|_{holding_2}$, for case (c) S_m , and for case (d) M . X_{train} is the corresponding reference quantity estimated by the virtual entity, e.g., for case (a) 0 nm, for case (b) 0 nm/s, for case (c) 0 mN/nm, and for case (d) M_{train} . The standard uncertainty of the difference, i.e., the denominator of Eq. (10.2), is obtained by combining the reproducibility of the system $u_{reproducibility}$, estimated during the P2V twinning, and the composition of uncertainty contributions as per the LPU [30] through the constitutive equations of nanoindentation, i.e. u_{GUM} [31] [32].

Conversely, quality controls for cases (f) and (g) are based, respectively, on s-control chart and on T²-Hotteling control chart for multivariate quality variables [33].

Case (d) provides an adaptation of typical s-control chart to cater for the measurement reproducibility of the noise proxy. In particular, limits of the control charts are adapted as:

$$UCL = \bar{s} + k \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{\bar{s}}{c_4} \sqrt{1 - c_4^2} \right)^2 + s_m^2(s)} \quad (10.5)$$

$$LCL = \bar{s} - k \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{\bar{s}}{c_4} \sqrt{1 - c_4^2} \right)^2 + s_m^2(s)} \quad (10.6),$$

where $\bar{s} = s(\varepsilon_F)_{train}$, and $s_m^2(s) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (s_i - \bar{s})^2}{m-1}$, with m being the number of indentations used to train the virtual entity model during the P2V twinning.

8.2 Validation methodology

The validation is performed relying on synthetic data and on empirical data. The DT scope is limited to a case in which verification of the measurement quality and the state-of-health of the measurement equipment is performed on a given material. In particular, demonstration of DT validity and of validation approach are performed considering candidate reference material, e.g. SiO₂ and W.

8.2.1 Synthetic data set validation

The virtual entity can also be exploited to generate synthetic datasets. Such datasets represent the ideal response of the instrument performing nanoindentation of a given material. Since the virtual entity embeds uncertainty evaluation, the synthetic datasets are generated catering for measurement noise.

Further, the parametric modelling allows introducing typical errors, e.g. see Figure 52. Full details of synthetic dataset generation within a metrological framework for nanoindentation exploiting the virtual entity are available in [34].

Validation is performed testing the quality control pipeline summarized in Section 10.1, against synthetic data.

Synthetic data representing the ideal response are expected to present no out-of-control, since the dataset generation exploits the virtual entity that establishes the

reference quantity. Thus, in no case the null hypothesis shall be rejected. In practice, considering a risk of error of I kind α , a maximum number of out-of-tolerance, i.e., false positives, are expected as $[\alpha m]$.

Additionally, synthetic errors are added to simulate: thermal drift, pop-in, and pop-out.

In particular, the virtual entity is established by P2V twinning relying on 16 indentations on calibrated reference SiO₂ sample, calibrated by NPL. Indentations consisted of loading, primary holding and secondary holding (at 10% of F_{max}), respectively, of 10 s, 8 s, 9 s and 60 s.

8.2.2 Empirical data set validation

Empirical data validation is performed by measuring datasets on two calibrated reference materials, i.e., SiO₂ and W, and making the working hypothesis of using either the one or the other to perform periodic indirect verification of the testing equipment. In such a conditions, the DT, independently, trained on the empirical datasets predicts ideal response for the two materials.

P2V twinning is performed performing a set of 21 indentations on SiO₂ and of 26 indentations on W. Indentations consisted of loading, primary holding and secondary holding (at 10% of F_{max}), respectively, of 10 s, 8 s, 9 s and 60 s.

Validation is performed collecting additional 25 indentations on SiO₂ and 16 on W. These indentations were collected immediately after the dataset used to establish the P2V twinning was performed. In such conditions, considering a risk of error of I kind α , a maximum number of out-of-tolerance, i.e., false positives, are expected as $[\alpha m]$.

Additionally, out of control conditions were experimentally generated to test DT capability of identifying errors and root causes. Table 9 summarizes the full experimental plan.

Table 9 Validation datasets for nanoindentation DT. CRF: Calibrated Reference Material. “m”: number of collected (or synthetically generated) indentations.

Validation	Training dataset	Validation dataset	Scope
Synthetic	Experimental; Anton Paar NHT system; m=16; CRF: SiO ₂	Synthetic (m=10)	Validation
		Synthetic thermal drift (m=10)	Validation identification of Thermal drift
		Synthetic pop-in (m=10)	Validation identification of pop-in
		Synthetic pop-out (m=10)	Validation identification of pop-out
Empirical	Experimental; Anton Paar NHT system; m=18 CRF: SiO ₂	Empirical (m=21)	Validation
		Empirical, with laboratory air conditioning off (m=46)	Validation identification of noise, thermal drift, shape change
		Empirical, with worn-out indenter (m=16)	Validation identification of shape change

Empirical	Experimental; Nanomechanics system; m=16 CRF: SiO ₂	Empirical (m=15)	Validation	
		Empirical, after cooling the sample of 2.5 °C (m=10)		Validation identification of thermal drift
		Empirical, after heating the sample of 0.4 °C (m=10)		
Empirical	Experimental; Anton Paar NHT system; m=25 CRF: W	Empirical (m=16), immediately after training	Validation	
		Empirical (m=16), 1 day after training	Validation and sensitivity to environmental conditions	

8.3 Validation Results

8.3.1 Synthetic data set validation

As Figure 53 to Figure 56 show, the synthetic data validation was successful, identifying no out-of-control when indentations are simulated in nominal conditions, and all indentations out-of-control, when a measurement error was synthetically added. Also, see Figures, quantities out-of-control are associated with the root cause of the error as described in Section 10.1.

Figure 53 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Synthetic data in nominal conditions. All points are inside the control limits.

Figure 54 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Synthetic data with negative thermal drift: notice in the panel related to “slope_holding_2” all the points are below the lower control limit.

Figure 55 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Synthetic data with pop-in introducing a discontinuity in the loading portion of the indentation curve: notice in the panel related to “T2_loading”, “residuals_loading” all the points are outside the upper control limit. Other out-of-controls depends on the changed loading shape.

Figure 56 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Synthetic data with pop-in introducing a discontinuity in the unloading portion of the indentation curve: notice in the panel related to “T2_unloading”, “residuals_unloading” all the points are outside the upper control limit. Other out-of-controls depends on the changed loading shape.

8.3.2 Empirical data set validation

First results on the DT for periodic verification on SiO₂ are presented and commented. When validating the DT in nominal conditions, see Figure 57, only 1 out of 21 indentations was identified as an out-of-control. This nominally is a false positive. Considering a risk of error $\alpha=5\%$, the expected false positive is 1, in line with the experimentally obtained results.

Figure 57 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on SiO₂ in nominal conditions: only 1 out of 21 indentations was identified as an out-of-control (see panel related to slope_holding_2).

Then, the DT is validated introducing error sources. First, the laboratory air conditioning was turned off. Results in Figure 58 show that the modified environmental conditions generate a change in the shape, and an increase in the noise. Accordingly 34.7% of indentations were identified as out-of-control. This result is in line with empirical expectation, since not necessarily, mechanical characteristics shall change with a varying change in the average room temperature. Then, indentations with a worn-out indenter were performed to test sensitivity to such error source. Results in Figure 59 show that all indentations are correctly identified as out of control due to the changed shape of the indentation curve, thanks to the T^2 control chart.

Figure 58 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on SiO_2 with air conditioning off to test sensitivity to increased noise. The modified environmental conditions generate a change in the shape, and an increase in the noise.

Figure 59 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on SiO_2 with worn-out indenter: all indentations are correctly identified as out of control due to the changed shape of the indentation curve, see panels “ T^2 ”.

Still working on SiO₂, the capability of the methodology to be applied to a different indentation platform was validated by considering a second training dataset to establish P2V twinning for a second indentation testing machine. Validation identified 1 out of 15 indentations as out of control, i.e. consistent with the maximum 1 false positive expected.

Figure 60 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on SiO₂ in nominal conditions for a second testing equipment: only 1 out of 15 indentations was identified as an out-of-control.

This second testing equipment was exploited to validate the DT capability of identifying severe thermal drifts induced by a substantial temperature difference between the sample and the indenter. Figure 61 and Figure 62 shows the DT quality control results highlighting severe thermal drifts and correctly identifying all the indentations as out-of-control.

Figure 61 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on SiO₂ for a cooled sample. All indentations are out-of-control: notice the thermal drift towards the thermal equilibrium in the “slope_holding_2” panel.

Figure 62 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on SiO₂ for a heated sample. All indentations are out-of-control: notice the thermal drift towards the thermal equilibrium in the “slope Holding_2” panel.

Last, validation on the capability of the methodology to be applied to a different CRF was investigated. The DT was trained to establish a P2V twinning for a periodic verification of the testing equipment based on W. Results show that the maximum number false positive is obtained, validating the procedure, and verifying the applicability to different testing equipment and to diverse periodic verification scenarios.

Figure 63 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on W in nominal conditions – data collected immediately after training: only 2 out of 16 indentations were identified as an out-of-control.

Figure 64 Validation Results of nanoindentation DT. Empirical data on W in nominal conditions – data collected 1 day after training: after the thermal stabilization (first 9 indentations) only 1 out of 16 indentations were identified as an out-of-control.

9 Internal Arc Test

Switchboards are critical components in electrical power distribution systems, responsible for the control, protection, and isolation of electrical circuits in industrial, commercial, and utility applications. Given the high-power levels involved, internal faults can lead to the formation of electric arcs, which rapidly release large amounts of thermal and mechanical energy. These events may result in severe damage to equipment and represent a significant hazard for personnel, making internal arc testing a key requirement in switchboard design and certification.

The motivation for the Internal Arc Test (IAT) DT is to improve the tests standardized by [35], [36] controlling the electrical power used as input in the physical environment and reducing the cost of implementing several experimental tests on different switchboards compartments of the same equipment, in order to identify the worst-case scenario. Also, the result from its digital counterpart will be used to extrapolate the test for higher voltage configurations.

9.1 Worse case identification

The short circuit withstand test was simulated using two methods. The Finite Difference Method (FDM) provides only the average value of the output pressure and temperature but can be resolved within a short time and with minimal computational resources. Instead, the Finite Volume Method (FVM) gives a detailed spatial description of the phenomenon, including the pressure, temperature, and air velocity, with the cost of requiring more computational time and resources. Although each method provides different outcomes, both methods are based on the same fundamental equations.

As stated in Section A.3.1 of [36], every compartment of the unit containing a main circuit component should be tested. In the case of modular units, the test must be conducted on two units connected as they would be in service. Furthermore, it also states that testing should be conducted in all compartments at the end of the switchgear adjacent to the indicators.

With this in mind, and given that the measurements of the input parameters mentioned in the previous section were taken from a randomly selected compartment with the characteristics described above, we can not only perform an FVM simulation of the overpressure and temperature for that volume, but we can also simulate the same output parameters for the rest of the compartments in the tested unit as if the arc was produced inside them.

From all the simulations with the same initial conditions, a comparison is made between the mean pressure distribution obtained from the FDM and the resistance of the walls and components inside each compartment. This comparison determines which new compartment should be tested next, the one with the maximum overpressure difference, or even the highest temperature, optimizing resource usage. Figure 65 shows the workflow of the proposed method.

Figure 65: P2V and V2P connections. The worst-case compartment is identified for further testing.

As shown in Figure 65, for the compartment chosen as the next one to be tested, an FVM simulation was performed. This simulation, using the same input parameters before updating the physical entity, will not only show the temperature and pressure distribution inside the unit but also the gas flow. This simulation can be used to improve the switchgear design or to detect potential future issues.

9.2 Models Implemented

As mentioned above, the short circuit withstand test was simulated using two methods, FDM and FVM. The first model provides only the average value of the output pressure and temperature but can be resolved within a short time and with minimal computational resources. Instead, the finite volume method gives a detailed spatial description of the phenomenon, including the pressure, temperature, and air velocity, with the cost of requiring more computational time and resources.

9.2.1 Finite difference method

This method is explained considering a switchgear with two compartments, one at high pressure (where the arc is produced), and the other where its air can flow, shown in Figure 66.

Figure 66: Schematic of the physical model. It shows the arc heat Q_1 , the mass m_i and volume V_i , the velocity components u_i , v_i and w_i , and the pressure p_i and temperature T_i , whit $i = \{1, 2, 3\}$ for each compartment. m_{12} and m_{23} are the mass fluxes between compartments.

Figure 66 shows a schematic of the physical model considering a switchgear with two compartments, one at high pressure (the “Arc Compartment”, where the arc is produced), and the other where the gas can flow (the “Exhaust Compartment”). The exhausted gas is ventilated to the “Installation Room”, a volume greatly bigger than the others two. The model can be represented from the equations of ideal gas, mass, momentum and energy conservation equations [37]. For each time step, the mass of the compartment is calculated with the current conditions of the system as

$$m(t_i) = \frac{p(t_i)V}{(c_v(\kappa-1)T(t_i))}, \quad (10)$$

where $p(t_i)$ and $T(t_i)$ are the pressure and temperature at the current time step, V is volume of the compartment, c_v is specific heat capacity at constant volume, and κ is heat capacity ratio. Then, the change in mass and temperature are calculated as

$$\Delta m = (m_{in} - m_{out})\Delta t, \quad (11)$$

where m_{in} and m_{out} are the mass flow into and out of the compartment, Δt is the simulation time step, and

$$\Delta T = \frac{\Delta Q + \Delta m_{in}(c_{p,high}T_{high}(t_i) - c_v T(t_i)) - \Delta m_{out}(c_p - c_v)T(t_i)}{m(t_i)c_v}, \quad (12)$$

where ΔQ is the volumetric heat energy source, Δm_{in} and Δm_{out} are the mass changes of the compartment with higher and lower pressure, $c_{p,high}$ is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure at the compartment with higher pressure, and c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of the compartment.

Finally, the mass, temperature and pressure for the next iteration is calculated as

$$m(t_{i+1}) = m(t_i) + \Delta m, \quad (13)$$

$$T(t_{i+1}) = T(t_i) + \Delta T, \quad (14)$$

$$p(t_{i+1}) = \frac{m(t_{i+1})c_v[\kappa-1]T(t_{i+1})}{V}. \quad (15)$$

9.2.2 Finite volume method

In this case, the mass, momentum, and energy conservation equations, as well as

the ideal gas model and the turbulence model, are calculated with the finite volume method [38].

Any simulation with the finite volume method needs three stages: the pre-process or mesh configuration, the simulation process, and the post-process or result visualization. In this work, each step was performed with different software, and they are briefly explained next considering the most important point for the application. The pre-process is made with the program GMSH [39] with which a .geo file is created. In this file, the geometry and mesh size configurations of the switchgear are defined.

When configuring the file, a volume outside the switchboard extruded from the surface where the fluid will be expelled (the safety valve) must be created. This surface must have a small volume of its own to improve the simulation of the flow, and it serves as a smooth transition between the inside of the switchboard and the outside. The size will depend on the area of the valve and the total volume of the simulated gas. Another point to consider is the mesh size near the exhaust surface. Because it is an area with a significant velocity and pressure gradient, a finer mesh must be made in this area. Although the sizes will depend on what is being simulated, a general rule is that the volume elements must be smaller in these areas. A finished drawing is presented in Figure 67.

The software OpenFOAM [40] is used for the simulation process; it works from a console command (no graphical interface version is available) and with a defined structured directory. An example directory tree can be seen in Figure 68. For a more detailed explanation of how to run a simulation, see the OpenFOAM User Guide [38]. Output values of pressure on specific zones can be obtained if a Monte Carlo simulation is going to be made later.

Finally, in the post-process, the output files are rendered and shown in a graphical interface with the software ParaView [41]. The pressure, temperature profiles, and velocity fields of the entire volume or a section can be seen with this software. Probes on specific zones can be placed to extract values along the complete simulation time.

Figure 67: Example of finished drawing and meshing plotted in GMSH. For simplicity, this is a side view of the 3D drawing. The vertices are represented as grey dots and with blue lines the segments which connect the vertices delimiting the different volumes. It can be seen how the mesh is denser at the top where a volume represents the exterior zone of the switchgear.

Figure 68: Example of directory tree of a project. The configuration of the solver, the constant values and BCs are located inside a case folder, the geometry meshed to use inside a mesh one, and two more files to run the simulation or clean output values when needed.

9.3 Monte Carlo Method for uncertainty estimation of overpressure

From the analysis of the model implemented, several uncertainties sources were identified, such as dimensional measurements, specific heat capacity, initial gas density, pressure and temperature, arc voltage and current, discharge coefficient, thermal transfer coefficient and laminar viscosity. Not all sources may be relevant in the uncertainty budget; a sensitivity analysis of the model was implemented.

Because the virtual entity can be simulated with a parametric model, the IAT DT will use the Monte Carlo Method (MCM, described in [42]) to obtain the mean and standard deviation of the overpressure.

To accomplish this, a dataset for each input parameter is generated using random samples with an appropriate known distribution type. From the output parameter's distribution, the value of the measurand is determined.

The different uncertainty sources described in the previous section, Table 10 and Table 11 list these sources. Note that not all sources will be measured in the physical environment and for those cases their distributions and typical values would be taken from literature. Table 11 shows the range informed in the literature for those parameters.

A sensitivity analysis was made with the implementation of the MCM to the FDM. As mentioned in [42], the distributions must have a size of at least $10^4 \cdot 1/(1-p)$ elements, where p is the confidence interval chosen for the calculus. For a 0.68 confidence interval ($k=1$), $3.1 \cdot 10^4$ elements are needed for each of the distributions for the input parameters mentioned with the mean and range values described. For the standard deviation, where is the standard deviation presented in Table 10.

Table 10: Uncertainties sources from the equations for the finite difference calculation. Normal distribution is considered with $k=2$.

Source	Symbol	Description	Probability distribution	Limit of distribution	Observation
Dimensional measurements	-	Resolution of the instruments and parallax error.	Rectangular	0.5 mm	Instrument resolution
Specific heat capacities	$c_v - c_p$	Deviations from a pure gas mixture.	Normal	1%	Literature
Initial gas density	ρ	Deviations from a pure gas mixture.	Normal	0.1%	Literature
Gas pressure	p	Initial pressures for ambient and compartment	Normal	5 hPa	Instrument accuracy
Voltage measurement	U	From the measurement instruments.	Normal	1%	Instrument accuracy
Current measurement	I	From the measurement instruments.	Normal	1%	Instrument accuracy
Gas temperature	T	Initial temperatures for ambient and compartment	Normal	1 K	Instrument accuracy

Table 11: Range of sources with rectangular probability distribution informed in the literature.

Source	Symbol	Description	Probability distribution	Range	Observation
Discharge coefficient	α_{out}	Coeff. that considers the shape of the opening.	Rectangular	0.6-0.75 (dimensionless)	Literature
Thermal transfer coefficient	k_p	Coeff. of electric energy to heat energy.	Rectangular	0.4-0.7 (dimensionless)	Literature
Laminar viscosity	μ	Deviations from a pure gas mixture.	Rectangular	(1.8-2.0) 10^{-5} Pa s	Literature

The result for the uncertainty calculation with a MCM with iterations for the pressure inside the arc compartment with all probability distributions for the sources included (now called Δp) was compared with the result of the uncertainty calculated with just one of the probability distributions and the rest of the sources as a constant value equal to the mean value of the original distribution. Each of the last ones was called Δp_j , where j corresponds to the name of each distribution. These results are presented in Figure 69 as the ratio of $\Delta p_j/\Delta p$. The values inside the exclusion zone in red can be neglected, and they will be excluded as an uncertainty source for the model. The 0.3 value corresponds to one third of the total uncertainty Δp , which for uncertainty values less or equal than that, the influence is negligible. In conclusion, the arc voltage and current (u_i and i_i with $i = \{R, S, T\}$ respectively), the thermal transfer coefficient (k_p) and the discharge coefficient (α) will be used as an uncertainty source.

Figure 69: Results for the sensitivity analysis with iterations for each simulation.

9.4 Validation measurements

The aim of these measurements is to compare experimental pressure data

measured inside the compartments of three switchgears configurations with the pressure evolution predicted by the FDM and FVM models at the same sensor locations. In addition, the temperature rise is measured at several points around the device to provide further comparison with the thermal predictions of the DT. For the Monte Carlo (MC) analysis, measurements of current and voltage are also recorded to characterize the electrical behavior of the arc and to quantify the variability of the input parameters.

9.4.1 Tested switchgear

Measurements are obtained for three different configurations (Cases A, B, and C), each representing a particular operational scenario of a switchgear. The dimensions of Case A are 60 x 30 x 60 cm, Cases B and C consist of two casings of 60 x 30 x 90 cm attached together. Figure 70 shows the two physical devices from which these three cases are derived. Figure 71 presents a transverse cross-section of the CAD model for both devices shown in Figure 70. Cases B and C correspond to the same device; however, Case C incorporates an additional internal barrier that modifies the fluid-flow path and, consequently, the pressure distribution inside the enclosure.

Besides the metal casing, another critical component of the switchgear is the rupture disc, whose design has a significant influence on the overall behavior of the test. The assembly consists of two screwed flanges with a lead disk 80 mm in diameter and 0.6 mm thick placed between them, as shown in Figure 72. The material and thickness of the disk were selected to achieve a rupture pressure of approximately 0.4 MPa, which remains well within the safe operating limits of the pressure sensor used in the experiments. In the DT, the rupture disc is explicitly represented through boundary conditions that govern the pressure relief mechanism. The experimentally determined rupture pressure is used as a triggering criterion for the opening of the outlet boundary, allowing a consistent comparison between the simulated and measured pressure evolution.

Figure 70: Devices to be used as case tests for validation of the models.

Figure 71: Transversal cut of both devices to be tested – (a) and (b) – and the third case (c) with an added metal sheet as a barrier for the fluid flow.

Figure 72: Close up of the rupture disc between the flanges, the pressure transmitter and a thermocouple.

9.4.2 Magnitudes to measure

During the tests, measurements of pressure, temperature, voltage, and current are acquired. Pressure is measured using a compact pressure transmitter (TPX-722), which is insensitive to rapid pressure fluctuations”, highly resistant to vibrations, and has an accuracy of $\pm 0.35\%$ FS. The transmitter is installed close to the rupture disc in order to capture the pressure evolution near the outlet of the device. Although the pressure inside the casing can be considered nearly homogeneous, the presence of steep pressure gradients in the vicinity of the outlet makes this location more suitable for capturing the maximum pressure values reached during the event.

Temperature measurements are performed using thermocouples placed at several locations inside the switchgear to quantify the internal thermal response. These measurements allow a direct comparison with the predictions of the DT, particularly with respect to the energy transfer from the electrical power of the arc

to thermal energy. Type E thermocouples, with an operating temperature range from $-270\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, are selected due to their high sensitivity. A small, welded junction is used to ensure a fast temporal response, which is required to accurately resolve the temperature rise occurring over a time interval of approximately 10 to 20 ms. A high sampling-rate data acquisition system is employed to capture the transient temperature evolution.

Finally, current and voltage measurements are obtained from the electrical circuit used to generate the arc synchronized with thermodynamic measurements to ensure a common temporal reference. These signals are recorded using dedicated electrical instrumentation provided by the laboratory and synchronized with thermodynamic measurements. The electrical data constitute key inputs for estimating the energy dissipated by the arc and are therefore essential for validating the arc heat source implemented in the DT.

9.4.3 Arc generation

The electric arc is generated by (ask the laboratory for the specific triggering mechanism). The arc is established between two connectors screwed to copper bars arranged as busbars. The separation distance between the bars and their effective length and thickness are selected based on empirical procedures and prior experience established by the testing laboratory, ensuring reproducible arc initiation and stable maintenance throughout the test duration. The electrical supply provides a nominal voltage of 230 V and a prospective short-circuit current of 14.5 kA.

The acquisition of pressure and temperature signals is triggered by the arc initiation, allowing the transient response of the system to be directly compared with the time-resolved predictions of the DT.

9.4.4 Test procedure

Each test follows a standardized procedure to ensure reproducibility. After the device is mechanically secured to the ground and the enclosure opening is firmly closed, the copper bars are connected to the electrical supply, the sensors are installed, and the rupture disc is properly mounted.

A preliminary test of the sensors is performed without triggering the electric arc in order to record the initial thermodynamic conditions. Subsequently, the arc is initiated, and the corresponding data is recorded. After arc extinction, a visual and mechanical inspection of the device is carried out to assess its structural integrity and to determine whether further tests can be performed using the same configuration, given the destructive nature of the experiment.

The experimental data obtained is used to compare pressure curves and temperature evolution with predictions of the DT. Metrics such as peak pressure, time to peak, and overall waveform shape are evaluated. These comparisons allow the level of agreement between experiments and simulations to be quantified and provide guidance for adjusting the arc model, heat transfer mechanisms, and fluid dynamics representations when necessary.

10 Quantum Voltage Standard

The objective of the DT is to optimize the configuration parameters [43], [44] of the physical system [45] to reduce setup and measurement times and optimize the transference of the SI voltage unit, the volt, to secondary standards. The Physical-to-Virtual (P2V) connection is determined by measurements on the physical system that feeds the data-driven model. This model uses Machine Learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict the configuration parameters that will serve as control signals in the Virtual-to-Physical (V2P) connection [46]. Figure 73 depicts these concepts.

Figure 73. Representation of the Quantum Voltage Standard DT.

Josephson voltage standards allow the generation of both DC and AC signals, enabling electrical voltages to be directly linked to the reference constants established by the International System of Units (SI) [44], according to:

$$V_J(t) = n(t)(h)/2ef, \quad (16)$$

Where $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ is the quantum state, f is a microwave frequency referred to an atomic clock, h is the Planck constant, and e is the elementary charge.

The Programmable Josephson Voltage Standard (PJVS) is a Josephson system that can be used as a superconducting multi-bit digital-to-analog converter (DAC). The PJVS produces stable DC voltages and time-stepwise approximated waveforms, whose accuracy is determined by well-defined constant voltage steps [44], given by equation (16). Figure 74 shows an example of an AC signal.

Figure 74. The red curve represents an ideal sine wave of 1 V peak with a frequency of 62.5 Hz. The blue curve shows the PJVS stepwise approximated signal with $n = 20$ steps per period.

Therefore, the main parameters to be optimized are:

Generated Josephson voltage [VJ], microwave frequency [fmw] and power [Pmw], array critical current [Ic], helium level [LHe] or cryocooler settings [s], synthesized signal frequency [fs], and the number of steps per period [N].

10.1 Proposed Methodology

To implement the V2P connection and establish a closed feedback loop for updating the DT, measurements should be integrated with the data-driven model to dynamically adjust the model based on the system's actual behavior. This requires the acquisition of data in real-time or a batch, a mechanism to update the DT based on new measurements, and an optimization process to adjust the controllable parameters iteratively.

The physical system has the following controllable parameters: signal amplitude [A], signal frequency [fs], number of steps [N], microwave frequency [fmw], microwave power [Pmw], critical current [Ic], sampling rate [SR], and number of points per period [Npp]. The initial configuration is used to generate the desired objective signal, according to equation (16).

The signal is sampled in a batch with the selected digitizer. Then, a classification algorithm detects measurements with anomalies and discards them, ensuring that only useful signals are used to create the datasets and train the data-driven model that predicts the system behavior based on the input parameters.

After training the model and making predictions, the error is calculated as the difference between the predicted and the theoretical signal. The uncertainty of the inputs is estimated with the Monte Carlo GUM-compliant method (MCM) [47]. For model uncertainty, the Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) [48] method is used. Then, an optimization algorithm adjusts some of the controllable parameters to reduce the difference between the predicted and theoretical signals. Updated parameters are set in the physical system to regenerate the signal. The system continuously refines parameters to achieve the desired performance. Figure 75 shows the workflow of the method used.

Figure 75. Proposed methodology for the Quantum Voltage Standard DT.

10.2 Selection of input parameters and evaluation of metrological characteristics

The input parameters define the uncertainty in the P2V connection. The Microwave frequency depends on the stability of Cesium and Rubidium atomic clocks and is measured with a frequency counter. The signal and sampling frequencies are affected by jitter, since they rely on the stability of a digital PLL and are also related to the atomic clocks.

The microwave power is estimated and verified with subsequent measurements using the calibration curve of the microwave synthesizer and the step width of the voltage-current characteristic curve. The current margin value can also be calculated using the step width.

The helium level is measured with a liquid helium level sensor, before and after running the experiment. This only applies in a wet system.

The gain and offset of the digitizers with their standard deviations are determined by previous characterizations. In the case of the custom-made $\Sigma\Delta$ digitizer [49], the gain and offset are calculated with an initial test signal.

The uncertainty of voltage measurements is related to the measuring instrument. We use high-accuracy instruments (Agilent 3458A, NI PXI5922, and a custom-made $\Sigma\Delta$ digitizer) to measure the QVS output and compare it with the DT output. Because linearization of the model provides an inadequate representation of the uncertainty, the inputs have low correlation, and their distributions are known, their uncertainty contribution is evaluated following the GUM, applying MCM [47].

The traceability for measurements is defined by the ISO/IEC 17025 standard [50]. As the QVS DT represents the realization of a unit of the SI, the volt (V), the traceability is guaranteed in the definition of the SI. As stated before, the voltage of this primary standard depends only on fundamental constants such as h (the Planck constant) and e (the elementary charge), and on a known microwave frequency. The latter is traceable to the unit second (s) of the SI by an atomic clock.

We evaluate the accuracy, repeatability, and sensitivity according to the measurement system by direct comparison with the SI unit. Fidelity is represented by the accuracy of voltage measurements of the theoretical Josephson voltage.

The twinning rate depends on the measurement duration, as the model produces an output after every measurement.

For sensitivity evaluation, the inputs are modified in small percentages according to the parameter, considering that the output variation must be greater than the digitizer's uncertainty. To evaluate the metrological characteristics of the parameters, we follow the definitions from the GUM [30] and VIM [51].

10.3 Model - Mixture Density Network (MDN)

The model was trained using TensorFlow [52] and Keras [53] to predict the quantum voltage steps of the signals.

A Mixture Density Network [54] is a neural network designed to model probability distributions over its outputs. Instead of predicting a single value (as in ordinary regression), an MDN predicts the parameters of a mixture model—usually a Gaussian mixture—so that for each input it outputs a full probability density. Figure 76 shows the model used for DC signals.

Mixture Density Network (MDN) with Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) Model

Figure 76. Mixture Density Network with Monte Carlo Dropout.

The architecture is as follows:

- **Input:** regular layers (Dense, Conv1D, etc.)
- **ANN Layers:** Any standard stack of hidden layers (dense, convolutional, recurrent, etc.) of the neural network.
- **Mixture heads:** Three parallel dense layers produce:
 - Logit outputs: mixing weights (probability of each Gaussian).
 - Means for each component.
 - Log-standard-deviations for each component.

- **Output:** For K Gaussians and predicting a single scalar, the model outputs K values for mixing weights, K values for means, and K values for standard deviations.

The loss function is the Negative Log-Likelihood (NLL). For each training point, it computes the likelihood of the true value under the predicted mixture distribution.

10.3.1 Model training procedure

1. Create a dataset with a representative sample of the signals that the system can generate, randomizing the order.
2. Separate target from features, generating a sequence-to-sequence series.
3. Separate between training (80%) and testing (20%) datasets.
4. Normalize the features using a scaler.
5. Create the model of the neural network (type of neural network, number of layers, number of neurons, dropout rate, activation function, optimizer, loss, metric, batch size, epochs).
6. Train the model with the training dataset.
7. Evaluate the predictions on the testing sets and calculate the metrics.

The outputs are a sequence of points that follow the sequence of the input.

10.4 Uncertainty contribution of relevant parameters

- Errors and uncertainties in the model: Different sources of errors and uncertainties in neural networks were investigated [55] and identified in these categories:
 - Numerical errors: These result from floating-point round-off errors from different computation orders in the neural network's calculations. This is dependent on the Python libraries used [53] [52].
 - Epistemic Uncertainty (Model Uncertainty): This arises from the model's limited knowledge of the data and can be reduced by providing more data.
 - Aleatoric Uncertainty (Data Uncertainty): Data bias due to lack of information and variability in system parameters. This results from noise inherent in the data and cannot be reduced by adding more data.

The uncertainty will be evaluated using Monte Carlo Dropout [48].

- Errors and uncertainties in the instruments: In the case of measurement instruments, the sources of error and uncertainty are:
 - Digitizer voltage measurements with Agilent 3458A, NI PXI5922 and $\Sigma\Delta$ digitizer. The uncertainties are defined in the manuals and from previous characterizations [49] [56] [57].
 - White and power line noise in the system [58].
 - Quantization error from Josephson system resolution: $\pm 72,5$ uV.
 - Microwave frequency measurement. This is related to the stability of Cesium and Rubidium clocks and was obtained from a test report of the

microwave synthesizer [56] [57].

- Cryocooler temperature measurements: extracted from calibration certificate, ± 4 mK.

The error of the voltage steps will be determined by comparing the predictions of the model with the theoretical voltage of the PJVS signal.

10.5 Statistical modelling of the influence factors

Table 12 shows the probability distribution and uncertainty contribution of the selected influence factors.

Table 12. List of influence factors, their probability distribution, and uncertainty contribution.

Influence factor	Symbol	Description	Probability distribution	Uncertainty contribution
Numerical errors	ϵ_{num}	Floating point round-off errors	Uniform	Type B
ML model uncertainty	σ_{ML}	From calculations	Normal	Combined (type A and B)
Voltage measurement	V_m	From the digitizers	Normal	Combined (type A and B)
Noise components	η	Noise influence on the measurement setup and measured data	Normal	Type A
Quantization error	ϵ_q	Josephson system resolution	Uniform	Type B
Microwave frequency measurement	f_{mw}	Related to atomic clocks	Normal	Combined (type A and B)
Cryocooler temperature measurement	T_{cc}	From temperature sensor	Normal	Combined (type A and B)

10.6 Uncertainty evaluation

After a sensitivity analysis and considering the impact of each error and uncertainty source, it was determined that the model sources are more critical than the instrument sources, with the epistemic uncertainty being the most predominant. This uncertainty is due to the model's limited knowledge and can be reduced with more data.

As stated previously, the uncertainty contribution of the inputs is evaluated following the GUM, applying MCM [47]. The Monte Carlo method is a powerful computational technique, used as a complement to the GUM, especially in complex or nonlinear models where the MCM simulates thousands of random scenarios, propagating the distributions of the inputs to obtain a distribution of results, while the traditional GUM method uses the propagation law to calculate the uncertainty, both being comparable and validatable with each other.

To apply the method, first we assign the probability distribution to the input quantity (measurements) based on the available knowledge; then determine an empirical discrete representation of the probability distribution for the output quantity, based on realization of a large number of artificial MC experiments propagating the possible realizations of inputs through the model to the possible realizations of outputs; and finally represent the best estimate of the output quantity as the mean of the predictions of the realizations and the evaluation of the associated standard uncertainty as the standard deviation of the predictions of the realizations.

The uncertainty of the neural network is evaluated using the Monte Carlo Dropout method [48]. MC Dropout is a method used to estimate uncertainties in neural network predictions by interpreting dropout, typically used as a regularization technique, as a form of Bayesian approximation. Dropout randomly deactivates neuron connections during training to prevent overfitting. By keeping dropout active during inference and performing multiple forward passes, the predictions become stochastic, effectively sampling from an approximate posterior distribution over the model's parameters.

To obtain a complete uncertainty quantification for the DT, we mix GUM MCM input perturbations with MC Dropout on an MDN to produce a decomposed predictive uncertainty (aleatoric, epistemic, input-induced) and a total predictive standard deviation. First, we draw many perturbed inputs (GUM MC) to account for measurement uncertainty in the inputs; for each perturbed input run multiple stochastic forward passes with dropout enabled (MC-Dropout) to capture model (epistemic) variability; the MDN output gives per-forward-pass aleatoric variance; then combine these by the law of total variance (and averaging) to produce per-time-step predictive mean and variance. Figure 77 illustrates the method.

Figure 77. Combined MC GUM and MC dropout method for uncertainty estimation in MDN neural networks.

The procedure to calculate the predictions and their uncertainty is as follows:

1. For each point in the signal to be predicted, extract M random values from the input data distribution (between 50 and 200).
 - a. Keep dropout active during test time (in inference mode).
 - b. Perform N stochastic forward passes for the same input (between 50 and 200) [48].
 - c. Collect the N predictions to compute the mean prediction (average the N outputs to get the final prediction), and the uncertainty (variance or standard deviation of the N predictions).
2. Calculate the final prediction (average of the M outputs) and the uncertainty (standard deviation of the M predictions).

Figure 78 depicts an example of a 1 V DC signal sampled at 20 kHz. The uncertainty can be reduced if the dropout rate is reduced during model training.

Figure 78. Uncertainty estimation of the model using MC GUM and the MC dropout method for a DC signal.

The error of the voltage steps is determined by comparing the predictions of the model with the theoretical voltage of the PJVS signal. Results show that the uncertainty is in the order of $10 \mu\text{V/V}$, the same order as the measurements.

10.7 Validation

To ensure the quality of our method, the DT validation is made by comparing the predictions of the data-driven model with traceable voltage measurements taken in a dynamic regime. Both results must agree within their confidence intervals. The laboratory follows the ISO 17025:2017 [50] to provide traceability and software validation, as stated in its section 6.5.1 and section 7.11.2. We compare the model's predictions with DC voltage measurements performed in the TÜBITAK UME and INTI PJVS systems.

The validation workflow checks three key aspects,

- Prediction Accuracy: How close predictions are to measured values.
- Uncertainty Calibration: How realistic uncertainty estimates are.
- Error Distribution: If residuals follow expected patterns.

10.7.1 Synthetic data generation model for validation

Another form of validation involves comparing the predictions of the data-driven

model with synthetic signals. We programmed a Python algorithm for a synthetic data generation model that produces PJVS signals measured with a digitizer. The flux diagram is presented in Equation (16) is used to generate stepwise approximated signals according to the desired parameters. In this case, different variations were used (parameters in red). Then, the gain and offset of the digitizer are applied, and white noise is added. Finally, the signal is convoluted with Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filters. This simulates the output filters of the digitizer that add the transients to the measured signal.

Figure 79. Algorithm block diagram for synthetic data generation of PJVS signals. Parameters in red have different values to provide variation in signal generation.

Parameter Variation

The signals were generated by modifying these parameters:

- Signal Type: Sine
- Amplitude: [0.5, 0.75, 1] V
- Signal Frequency: [15.625, 31.25, 62.5] Hz
- Number of Steps: [8, 16, 20]
- Phase: 0
- Offset: 0
- Microwave Frequency: [69.9, 69.95, 70, 70.05, 70.1] GHz
- Segments Configuration: [4096, 2048, 1024, 512, 256, 256]
- Points per Period: [1040, 1200, 2000, 2400]
- Periods: 1
- Digitizer Gain: 0.9739647
- Digitizer Offset: [-2.005] mV
- White Noise: [2.8e-7, 2.9e-7, 3.0e-7, 3.1e-7] V

Combining all the values results in 2160 different signals that can be used to train the model. The result of some of the generated signals was compared with measured signals, as can be seen in Figure 80.

Figure 80. Synthetic data generation of PJVS signals. Comparison with a measured signal.

10.7.2 Validation metrics

The metrics computed across all predictions to validate the DT are:

- **Residuals:** Difference between predictions and measurements, it's the error per sample and output step.
- **RMSE:** Root Mean Squared Error. Penalizes large errors heavily. Small values are better.
- **MAE:** Mean absolute error. Average prediction error magnitude. Less sensitive to outliers and more interpretable than RMSE.
- **Mean of Residuals (Bias):** Tells if the model is systematically over/under-predicting. It should be near 0.
- **Standard deviation of Residuals:** Indicates how variable the errors are. Ideally matches the mean of the uncertainty.
- **Coverage:** This counts the fraction of points where the true value falls inside the interval $\mu \pm 1.96 \sigma$. The use of 1.96 assumes residuals (prediction errors) are approximately Gaussian so that 95% of the residuals are within $\pm 1.96\sigma$. If coverage is close to 0.95, the uncertainties are well calibrated (given the Gaussian assumption). If coverage $< 95\%$, uncertainties are too narrow (underconfident). If coverage $> 95\%$, uncertainties are too wide (overconfident).

To visualize and interpret the metrics, the following plots are studied:

- **Residuals vs Predicted (heteroscedasticity check):** If the model is well-specified, the residuals should scatter around zero with no pattern; the spread (variance) should be roughly constant if errors are homoscedastic. If residual spread grows/shrinks with predicted value heteroscedasticity should reflect that. If σ is large where residuals are large, that means that uncertainty is informative. Systematic non-zero mean trend (bias) indicates model bias dependent on magnitude.
- **Residuals histogram:** If the distribution is roughly Gaussian centered near zero, it should be bell-shaped and symmetric around zero. The MAE and RMSE are consistent with that shape.

- **Quantile-Quantile plot (probability plot vs Gaussian):** compares residuals to a theoretical normal distribution. If points fall on the diagonal, the residuals are approximately Gaussian. Deviations in the tails (heavy/light tails) indicate extreme errors compared to the normal distribution and the presence of outliers. This matters because coverage computed with $\pm 1.96 \sigma$ assumes normality.
- **Time series with $\pm 1.96 \sigma$ band:** This shows whether predicted trajectories follow measured values and whether the 95% band often contains the ground truth. If the measured curve is frequently outside the band, the uncertainties are underestimated. If the band is too wide everywhere, the uncertainties are overestimated (low information, the model is conservative). Periods where predictions systematically lag or lead actuals show a model dynamic mismatch.

10.7.3 TÜBITAK UME PJVS signal validation

We tested DC signals of 1 V, 100000 points measured at 20 kHz, and an aperture time of 25 μs . Table 13 shows the results.

Table 13. Results of validation calculations for the TÜBITAK UME PJVS system.

RMSE (μV)	5.657
MAE (μV)	4.529
Mean residual (μV)	-2.784
Std residual (μV)	4.838
Max absolute residual (μV)	23.718
Coverage (%)	99.99

Figure 81. Comparison between TÜBITAK UME DC measurement and the predictions with uncertainty.

Results show a small bias in the predictions and that the model is overconfident (uncertainties too wide).

Residuals vs Predicted

Figure 82. Residuals vs predicted voltage.

We can see a linear trend in the residuals.

Residuals histogram

Figure 83. Residuals histogram

The histogram shows that the residuals have a Gaussian shape, and the negative bias in the predictions.

Quantile-Quantile plot

Figure 84. Quantile-Quantile plot

The Q-Q plot confirms the Gaussian distribution because points are distributed in the red line $y=x$.

Time series plot

Figure 85. Time series plot.

The wide shaded area shows the overconfidence of the model. The predictions are conservative and near the mean of the measured voltages.

10.7.4 INTI PJVS signal validation

We tested DC signals of 1.023 V, 4000 points measured with an aperture time of 0.5 s.

Table 14. Results of validation calculations for the INTI PJVS system.

RMSE (nV)	74
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MAE (nV)	57
Mean residual (nV)	29
Std residual (nV)	67
Max absolute residual (nV)	368
Coverage (%)	98.80

Figure 86. Comparison between INTI DC measurement and the predictions with uncertainty.

As in the previous case, results show a small bias in the predictions. Model represents accurately the measurements.

Residuals vs Predicted

Figure 87. Residuals vs Predicted voltage.

We can see a linear trend in the residuals.

Residuals histogram

Figure 88. Residuals histogram.

Here the histogram shows that the residuals have a Gaussian shape with deformations in the tails, which indicates the presence of outliers. There is a positive bias in the predictions.

Quantile-Quantile plot

Figure 89. Quantile-Quantile plot.

The Q-Q plot confirms the presence of outliers because points depart from the red line $y=x$ in the tails.

Time series plot

Figure 90. Time series plot.

The wide shaded area shows the overconfidence of the model. The predictions are very conservative and near the mean of the measured voltages.

We show that in both cases the model and its uncertainty represent the measurements accurately, regardless of whether the predictions are conservative and near the mean of the measured voltages, or the uncertainty is a little overconfident. Metrics are consistent with measurements in each case.

11 High voltage cable system

11.1 Introduction

With this DT, studies on transmission and distribution insulated cable systems can be carried out, and their behaviour can be tested and optimized in a dynamic mode. The detailed knowledge of the real cable systems behaviour, without the need for physical interaction with them, provides support in the design and maintenance processes of these assets, which are key to the proper functioning of high-voltage electrical grids.

Another feature of this versatile DT comes into play, when it is used as a diagnostic tool in monitoring systems of isolated cable lines. In this case, by processing data on voltage and currents in the main conductors, ambient temperature in their surroundings and sheath-induced currents at strategic points in the installation, potential defects in the grounding systems can be detected autonomously.

As a result of this development, a GD is made available to electrical companies, which is useful for taking informed decisions to optimize the operation of insulated cable systems throughout their entire life cycle.

The DT of insulated high-voltage cable systems intended for the calculation and monitoring of the sheath currents has been tested and validated in the following two scenarios (two insulated power cable systems of different voltage level).

- The first one is a 220 kV transmission line with the sheaths also in cross-bonding configuration.
- The second cable system is a 400 kV power line with the sheaths connected in cross-bonding configuration, which is a typical example of a transmission line transporting great amounts of power.

For each case, a summary of the power line characteristics is presented. After this, the probability distributions and general data to take into account for the uncertainties of the DT are specified. Finally, the uncertainty results determined with the Monte Carlo method are compared with real readings acquired from the three power lines. The validation of the DT performance is carried out by checking the convergence between the calculations of the DT and the actual readings.

11.2 Methodology applied for the DT validation

In a first step, each power line is modelled according to the specifications given by the assets manufacturers and by the line owners. These specifications include data regarding the cables and their accessories (joints and terminals), as well as their laying configuration, including distances, the number of sections, where the sheaths are earthed and how the sheaths are connected.

Once the model is implemented in the DT, the uncertainty of the results is determined applying the Monte Carlo method. For this method application, the algorithm used for the uncertainty estimation is configured in the DT software

itself. Thus, for all the uncertainty sources (input variables) considered, their value/s, type of probability distribution and intervals for their characteristic reference variation are set up through the DT interface.

The Monte Carlo Method is applied according to the indications explained in the good practices guide corresponding to the Deliverable D2 [27] of this project.

The uncertainty estimation for this DT needs to be performed for each cable system scenario to be simulated. Once a power line is modelled, the DT can be executed in two different modes, static and dynamic. For the execution of the Monte Carlo statistical analysis in static mode, the suitable number of iterations considered to reach an accurate uncertainty estimation is set at 10,000. Due to the high computational requirements needed in the dynamic mode, for this case 1,000 executions are considered sufficient to provide a reliable uncertainty estimation.

For each considered power line, operating scenario and time instant, the average value and the uncertainty of the output variable sheath current is determined when the DT is run either in static or in dynamic mode.

The uncertainty can be assessed by calculating the percentiles of interest. In this way, for a 95% of assurance, the 2,5 and 97,5 percentiles are determined. The uncertainty can also be calculated by adjusting the output for each time instant to a normal distribution and determining its standard deviation. In this case, given that uniform distributions have been established for some of the input variables, it has been deemed more appropriate to apply the first approach.

The mean values obtained along with their uncertainty are plotted for a certain operating scenario in a considered time period of one day. In this way, the interval of possible values to be compared for validation purposes with real measured sheath currents can be visualized.

For the DT validation, the real sheath current measurements along with their uncertainty are superimposed in the previous plot. The uncertainty of the measured values is determined considering the accuracy of the sensors implemented in the cable systems. For the three cable systems considered for the DT validation, the uncertainty estimated in the real sheath currents measurements includes a 95% of confidence. Therefore, there will be two areas plotted, one corresponding to the calculated sheath currents uncertainties and another corresponding to the real measurements uncertainties.

If the two areas have an overlap zone in all the time instants, it can be considered that the DT successfully converges with the physical cable system. The best results of convergence are obtained for sheath currents above the threshold of 4-5 A. This is because with smaller current values, the relative deviations have an increasingly significant weight in the deviations of the final result, making the convergence with the measured values more difficult.

11.3 220 kV power line with cross-bonding configuration

11.3.1 Power line characteristics

The 220kV line modelled with the DT is shown in Figure 91. In this case, the image shown was taken directly from the line configuration interface of the DT software. This is a completely underground power line with a transmission capacity of 470 MVA. Along its entire length, the sheaths are connected following the cross-bonding configuration. This line connects two substations, named SubA and SubB. The electrical power flow is bidirectional, but for this given example SubA is modelled as the power source and SubB as the load. For the validation of the DT the complete line was modelled.

Figure 91. Layout of the 220 kV power line configured in the DT SPACS interface.

In all the cross-bonding sections there are differential sensors installed in all the joints with ground connection; thus, the sheath currents are measured in all the mayor sections and in the three phases. Furthermore, the sheath currents are measured at the beginning and at the end of the power line. In addition, the currents in the active conductors are measured at the beginning of the line, that is, at position SubA.

The active conductor of the insulated cables used in this power line is of copper and has a section of 2,000 mm². The sheath is also of copper and has a section of 315 mm². The dielectric is of XLPE, and its outer cover is of polyethylene (PE). The cable system consists of a total of 15 minor sections. The cables are positioned in a staggered arrangement. The minor sections lengths (obtained from the project specifications), the type of sheaths connections and the major sections are indicated in Table 15.

Minor section	Initial joint	End joint	Length (m)	Major section
1	SubA	CE1	412,42	SubA-CE3 (cross-bonding)
2	CE1	CE2	418,59	
3	CE2	CE3	417,07	
4	CE3	CE4	680,54	CE3-CE6 (cross-bonding)
5	CE4	CE5	692,75	
6	CE5	CE6	679,72	
7	CE6	CE7	662,93	CE6-CE9 (cross-bonding)
8	CE7	CE8	662,92	
9	CE8	CE9	634,62	
10	CE9	CE10	668,14	CE9-CE12 (cross-bonding)
11	CE10	CE11	667,90	
12	CE11	CE12	667,42	
13	CE12	CE13	438,21	CE12-SubB (cross-bonding)
14	CE13	CE14	466,60	
15	CE14	SubB	464,06	

Table 15. Insulated power line minor sections, lengths, type of sheaths connections and major sections.

To model the power line, the mayor sections must be introduced. To do so, the components shown in Table 16 are selected from the interface section of the DT.

TYPE OF SECTION	SOURCE	LOAD
Cross-Bonding Section	Voltage source with far earth reference	Triphasic load

Table 16. Selected components from the DT interface section.

11.3.2 Considerations for the uncertainty determination

To determine the uncertainty of the DT output variable sheath current, the uncertainty variables indicated in Table 17 were considered. The variables thermal diffusion and initial temperature are only used in dynamic DT execution mode of the DT. The probability distribution type indicated was assigned to the input variables. For the uniform distributions, the expected variability limits are specified. In addition, the expected mean value and standard deviation are specified for the gaussian distributions.

Input uncertainty variable	Type of distribution	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Units
Thermal resistivity (ρ_{thermal}) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	0,8	1,2	K·m/W
Thermal diffusion (α_{thermal}) ⁽²⁾	Uniform	--	--	0,3e-6	0,5e-6	m ² /s
Electrical resistivity ($\rho_{\text{electrical}}$) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	0,98	1,02	p.u.
Relative permittivity (ϵ_r) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	0.9	1.05	p.u.
Ambient temperature (θ_{amb}) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	18	22	°C
Section length variation ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	-1	1	%
Voltage variation (U) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	-10	10	%
Diameter variation (of each layer) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	-2	2	%
Positions variation (of each cable) ^{(1) (2)}	Uniform	--	--	-1	1	%
Initial temperature ⁽²⁾	Gaussian	35	15%	--	--	°C
Current (active conductor) ^{(1) (2)}	Gaussian	100	3	--	--	%

Table 17. Uncertainty variables considered in the Monte Carlo method, type of probability distributions, expected variabilities (uniform distributions) and mean values and standard deviations (gaussian distributions).

(1) Uncertainty variable considered in the execution of the DT in static mode.

(2) Uncertainty variable considered in the execution of the DT in dynamic mode.

11.3.3 Uncertainty analysis results and DT validation

For the validation of the DT performance, the sheath currents calculated in dynamic mode were compared with the real measurements. In addition, for this first case, the study is also performed running the Monte Carlo method in static mode. This allows to calculate the currents in discrete time instants. With this, it can be evaluated how dynamic calculations improve the results compared to the static calculations.

For the validation of the DT performance, the sheath currents calculated in the static and dynamic modes were compared with real measurements. The sheath currents mean values along with their associated uncertainty were calculated for a specific power transmission of the cable system, in a 24-hour period of a given day.

The validation was performed by considering the calculated and measured sheath currents obtained for the positions SubA and SubB of the cable system. For the analysis of the results, the calculated mean values were plotted together with the corresponding measured values.

For the DT validation operating in static mode, the results obtained in the line positions SubA and SubB are presented in Figure 92 and Figure 93, respectively. The currents and associated uncertainties are calculated every hour. The dark and light green shades indicate the 63% and 95% of confidence, respectively. The minimum and maximum values are indicated too. On the other hand, the brown curves show the values of the measured currents and the dark and light brown shades indicate the 63% and 95% of confidence, respectively.

Figure 92. Calculated current applying the Monte Carlo (MC) method with the DT operating in static mode and measured current with their associated uncertainty for the line position SubA.

Figure 93. Calculated current applying the Monte Carlo (MC) method with the DT operating in static mode and measured current with their associated uncertainty for the line position SubB.

Analyzing the results obtained in static mode in both positions (SubA and SubB) and for the three phases, it can be stated that the discrete mean values of the sheath currents, together with their uncertainty range, have an overlap zone with the area defined for the measured values.

Concerning the position SubA, the average deviation obtained in amps was 0.94, 2.6, and 1.4 for phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the average uncertainty of the calculated values in amps obtained for the three phases was 2.9

in the three cases.

Concerning the position SubB, the average deviation obtained in amps was 1.1, 2.7, and 1.9 for phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the average uncertainty of the calculated values in amps obtained for the three phases was 2.7 in the three cases.

Similar results to those shown for positions SubA and SubB were obtained for the other positions of the cross-bonding cable system.

For the DT validation operating in dynamic mode, the results obtained in the line positions SubA and SubB are presented in Figure 94 and Figure 95, respectively. In these figures, the dark blue curve shows the mean values of the calculated currents by applying the Monte Carlo method, the dashed lines define the limits of the uncertainty area (100% of confidence), and the dark and light blue shades indicate the 63% and 95% of confidence, respectively. All the graphs showing the results represent the values obtained every 15 minutes.

Figure 94. Calculated current applying the Monte Carlo (MC) method with the DT operating in dynamic mode and measured current with their associated uncertainty for the line position SubA.

Figure 95. Calculated current applying the Monte Carlo (MC) method with the DT operating in dynamic mode and measured current with their associated uncertainty for the line position SubB.

Analyzing the results obtained in dynamic mode in both positions (SubA and SubB) and for the three phases, it can be stated that in all cases the two areas plotted have an overlapping zone.

As in both cases (static and dynamic mode) there are overlapping zones throughout

the entire time period, it can be stated that the DT successfully converges with the physical cable system and thus, its performance is validated once again.

Concerning the position SubA, the average deviation obtained in amps was 0.7, 1.2, and 1.0 for phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the average uncertainty of the calculated values in amps obtained for the three phases was 2.7, 2.9, and 2.4, respectively.

Concerning the position SubB, the average deviation obtained in amps was 0.8, 1.4, and 1.0 for phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the average uncertainty of the calculated values in amps obtained for the three phases was 2.6, 2.9, and 2.6, respectively.

Similar results to those shown for positions SubA and SubB were obtained for the other positions of the cross-bonding cable system.

11.4 400 kV power line with cross-bonding configuration

In this subsection, the validation of the DT with a 400 kV power line with cross-bonding configuration is presented.

11.4.1 Power line characteristics

The 400kV line modelled with the DT interface is shown in Figure 96. In this line, the cable system section with the cross-bonding configuration is connected at both ends to the respective sections in single point, which in turn are connected to two overhead lines.

Although the validation of the DT is performed for the cable section with the cross-bonding configuration, the complete line was modelled, since the line's operation in the other sections (single point and overhead line) can affect in the sheath currents determination.

Figure 96. Layout of the 400kV power line.

Among all the sections that make up the cross-bonding part of the power line, the first major section, which lies between positions C1 and C4, has been considered for this validation study (see Figure 97).

In this first cross-bonding section there are sensors installed in all the joints; thus, the sheath currents are measured in the three minor sections and in the three phases. Furthermore, the currents are measured at the beginning and at the end of each minor section. In addition, the currents in the active conductors are measured at the beginning of the cable section in cross-bonding, that is, at position CT0. The sensors emplacement is indicated in detail in Figure 97.

Figure 97. Layout of the cable system with the cross-bonding configuration and considered section for the DT validation indicating the sensors position.

To model the power line, the mayor sections must be introduced. To do so, the components shown in Table 18 are selected from the interface section of the DT.

TYPE OF SECTION		SOURCE	LOAD
Cross-Bonding	Single Point	Voltage source with far earth reference	Triphasic load

Table 18 Selected components from the DT interface section.

Figure 98 shows the image of the power line taken directly from the line configuration interface of the DT software.

Figure 98. Layout of the cable system configured with the cross-bonding configuration for the DT validation.

The active conductor of the insulated cables used in this power line is of copper and has a section of 2,500 mm². The sheath is also of copper and has a section of 250 mm². Furthermore, the dielectric is of cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE).

The cable systems with the single point and cross-bonding configurations consist of a total of 17 minor sections. The cables are positioned in a vertical arrangement. The minor sections lengths (obtained from the project specifications), type of sheaths connections and the major sections are indicated in Table 19.

Minor section	Initial joint	End joint	Length (m)	Major section
1	CT0	C1	390	CT0-C1 (single point)
2	C1	C2	781	C1-C4 (cross-bonding)
3	C2	C3	797	
4	C3	C4	856	
5	C4	C5	824	
6	C5	C6	808	C4-C7 (cross-bonding)
7	C6	C7	830	
8	C7	C8	783	
9	C8	C9	805	C7-C10 (cross-bonding)
10	C9	C10	846	
11	C10	C11	749	
12	C11	C12	814	C10-C13 (cross-bonding)
13	C12	C13	806	
14	C13	C14	831	
15	C14	C15	822	C13-C16 (cross-bonding)
16	C15	C16	649	
17	C16	CT6	312	

Table 19. Insulated power line minor sections, lengths, type of sheaths connections and major sections.

11.4.2 Considerations for the uncertainty determination

The calculation process of the uncertainty associated with DT is linked to the functionality of the DT itself and is based on the Monte Carlo method.

To determine the uncertainty of the DT output variable sheath current, the 11 uncertainty variables indicated in the first column of Table 20 were considered. For the uncertainty calculation process, a probability distribution type is assigned to each of the input variables. If the distribution considered is uniform, an expected variability bounded between a minimum and maximum value is specified. On the other hand, if the distribution considered is gaussian, an expected mean value and standard deviation are specified.

Input uncertainty variable	Type of distribution	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value	Units
Thermal resistivity (ρ_{thermal})	Uniform	--	--	0,8	1,2	K·m/W
Thermal diffusion (α_{thermal})	Uniform	--	--	0,3e-6	0,5e-6	m ² /s
Electrical resistivity ($\rho_{\text{electrical}}$)	Uniform	--	--	0,98	1,02	p.u.
Relative permittivity (ϵ_r)	Uniform	--	--	0.9	1.05	p.u.
Ambient temperature (θ_{amb})	Uniform	--	--	18	22	°C
Section length variation	Uniform	--	--	-1	1	%
Voltage variation (U)	Uniform	--	--	-10	10	%
Diameter variation (of layers)	Uniform	--	--	-2	2	%
Positions variation (of cables)	Uniform	--	--	-1	1	%
Initial temperature	Gaussian	50	15%	--	--	°C
Current (measured in the active conductor)	Gaussian	100	3	--	--	%

Table 20. Uncertainty variables considered in the Monte Carlo method, type of probability distributions, expected variabilities (uniform distributions) and mean values and standard deviations (gaussian distributions).

11.4.3 Uncertainty analysis results an DT validation

For the validation of the DT performance, the sheath currents calculated in dynamic mode were compared with real measurements. In the comparison process, the sheath currents mean values along with their associated uncertainty were calculated for a specific power transmission of the cable system, in a 24-hour period of a given day.

The validation was performed by considering the calculated and measured sheath currents obtained for the positions C2 (right side) and C3 (right side) of the cable system.

For the analysis of the results, for each phase, the calculated mean values were plotted together with the corresponding measured values, considering in both cases their associated uncertainties.

The limits for the measured currents are established considering an uncertainty of 10%. This value is determined based on the usual resolution of the sensors used in monitoring systems and taking into account that the values in the line under consideration are usually low, so they are measured at the lower part of the sensors scale. In all the figures with the graphs of results, the brown curve shows the value of the measured current in the corresponding phase. The dark and light brown shades indicate the 63% and 95% of confidence, respectively.

For the DT validation operating in dynamic mode, the results obtained in the line positions C2 and C3 are presented in Figure 99 and Figure 100, respectively. In these figures, the dark blue curve shows the mean values of the calculated currents by applying the Monte Carlo method, the dashed lines define the limits of the uncertainty area (100% of confidence), and the dark and light blue shades indicate the 63% and 95% of confidence, respectively. All of the graphs showing the results represent the values obtained every 15 minutes.

Figure 99. Calculated current applying the Monte Carlo (MC) method with the DT operating in dynamic mode and measured current with their associated uncertainty for the line position C2.

Figure 100. Calculated current applying the Monte Carlo (MC) method with the DT operating in dynamic mode and measured current with their associated uncertainty for the line position C3.

Analyzing the results obtained in dynamic mode in both positions (C2 and C3) and for the three phases, it can be stated that in all cases the two areas plotted have an overlapping zone throughout the entire time period, so it can be concluded that the

DT successfully converges with the physical cable system and thus, its performance is validated.

Concerning the position C2, the average deviation obtained in amps (mean of the measured values minus the calculated values) was 10.6, 15.1, and 7.3 for phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the average uncertainty of the calculated values in amps obtained for the three phases was 18.3, 14, and 16.7, respectively.

Concerning the position C3, the average deviation obtained in amps (mean of the measured values minus the calculated values) was 12.6, 6.1, and 5.3 for phases 1, 2, and 3, respectively. On the other hand, the average uncertainty of the calculated values in amps obtained for the three phases was 14.5, 19.7, and 17.9, respectively.

Similar results to those shown for positions C2 and C3 were obtained for the other positions of the cross-bonding cable system.

11.5 Conclusions

For the validation of the DT for the sheath currents in high voltage insulated cables, two systems have been considered. These cable systems are representative of transmission power lines typically used in the power grid. Their relevant characteristics for modelling them in the DT have been specified, along with the considered uncertainties for all the inputs variables. This allows to execute the Monte Carlo method to obtain an uncertainty estimation. These results given by the DT are compared with real measurements from the utilities analyzed.

The comparison between the real measurements and the Monte Carlo results is carried out by considering the uncertainty of both the results and the measurements. This uncertainty is plotted as an area around the measurements and the DT average result. It has been confirmed that there is an overlapping zone between the two areas, therefore the DT is validated.

To validate the DT it has to be executed in dynamic mode. However, for the first case study, it has also been executed in static mode, obtaining results for 24 individual time instants (one hour apart). This allows to check that the average deviation between the real measurements and the DT calculations is smaller in dynamic mode than in static mode. Therefore, it has been confirmed that the implementation of the dynamic calculations in the DT provides better results and improved functionality to the DT.

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